

Magic Squares of Order 12 Representing Days and Dates of the Year 2025

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The whole work as pdf files is available at author's sites:
<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=16068>

This work is without use of any kind of programming language

Abstract

*This work brings **dates** and **days of the year** 2025 in terms of magic squares of order 12 for the month of **July 2025**. Four different types of magic squares of order 12 are considered. Most of them are based on **cornered**, **single-digit bordered** and **double-digit bordered** magic squares. In all these cases, the respective **magic rectangles** are of equal sums. All the examples represents **dates** in two different ways, and the **days of the year** are represented by **magic sums**. The dates are considered as few entries of each magic square. For similar kind of work for the orders 3 to 11 refer author's work [30, 31, 32, 33, 34].*

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1 Introduction

In the previous papers [30, 31, 32, 33, 34], the author worked in representing **days** and **dates** of the year 2025 for the magic squares of orders 3 to 11. Let's call this kind of work as **reduced or less entries** magic squares. A short idea of this kind of representations for orders 3, 4 and 5 can be seen in F. Gaspalou web-site [3], where the representations are in terms of **magic sums**. This work brings the results in general forms for the the magic squares of order 12. In all the cases, the magic sum represents **days of the year** and **dates** are represented by few entries. The entries are non-sequential positive or negative numbers. For more details refer author's work [30, 31, 32, 33, 34].

This work brings **dates** and **days** of the year 2025 in terms of magic squares of order 12 for the months of **July, October** and **December, 2025**. It is based on **reduced entries** for the magic squares of order 12. In this work we have considered **four** different types of magic squares of order 12. These are based on **single-digit bordered, double-digit bordered** and **cornered** magic squares. The details are summarized as given below:

- (i) The **first type** is a **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 12 embedded with **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 8. The internal magic square is of order 4. The magic rectangles of orders 2×4 and 2×8 are of equal width and length in each case.
- (ii) The **second type** is a **cornered** magic square of order 12, where the magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8 and 10 are in the left upper corner. The magic rectangles of orders 2×4 , 2×6 , 2×8 and 2×10 are of equal width and length for each case.
- (iii) The **third type** is a **cornered** magic square of order 12 with **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 8 at the upper left corner embedded with a magic square of order 4. The four magic rectangles of orders 2×4 are of equal width and length. Also the magic rectangles of orders 2×8 and 2×10 are of equal width and length in each case. It also contains a magic square of order 10.
- (iv) The **forth type** is also a **cornered** magic square of order 12 with **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 10 at the upper left corner embedded with a **cornered** magic square of order 6 containing magic square of order 4. The magic rectangles of orders 2×4 , 2×6 and 2×10 are of equal width and length in each case.

Above we have given only the idea of four types of reduced entries magic squares. Actually, there are much more possibilities. These shall be seen at author's another work [36].

2 Magic Squares of Order 12

Below are six different examples of magic squares of order 12.

Example 2.1. *Let's consider a magic square of order 12*

1	pan	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870
870	98	1	51	72	22	119	78	28	125	140	43	93	870
870	3	50	97	118	71	24	124	77	30	45	92	139	870
870	49	99	2	23	120	70	29	126	76	91	141	44	870
870	131	34	84	87	37	134	57	7	104	113	16	66	870
870	36	83	130	133	86	39	103	56	9	18	65	112	870
870	82	132	35	38	135	85	8	105	55	64	114	17	870
870	67	117	20	5	102	52	47	144	94	73	123	26	870
870	21	68	115	100	53	6	142	95	48	27	74	121	870
870	116	19	69	54	4	101	96	46	143	122	25	75	870
870	88	138	41	32	129	79	14	111	61	58	108	11	870
870	42	89	136	127	80	33	109	62	15	12	59	106	870
	137	40	90	81	31	128	63	13	110	107	10	60	870
	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

It is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 12, where the blocks of order 3 equal **semi-magic** sums **semi-magic** squares.

Example 2.2. *Let's consider a magic square of order 12*

2	pan	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870
870	7	140	1	142	15	132	9	134	23	124	17	126	870
870	2	141	8	139	10	133	16	131	18	125	24	123	870
870	144	3	138	5	136	11	130	13	128	19	122	21	870
870	137	6	143	4	129	14	135	12	121	22	127	20	870
870	31	116	25	118	39	108	33	110	47	100	41	102	870
870	26	117	32	115	34	109	40	107	42	101	48	99	870
870	120	27	114	29	112	35	106	37	104	43	98	45	870
870	113	30	119	28	105	38	111	36	97	46	103	44	870
870	55	92	49	94	63	84	57	86	71	76	65	78	870
870	50	93	56	91	58	85	64	83	66	77	72	75	870
870	96	51	90	53	88	59	82	61	80	67	74	69	870
	89	54	95	52	81	62	87	60	73	70	79	68	870
	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

It is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 12, where the blocks of order 4 equal magic sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4.

Example 2.3. Let's consider a magic square of order 12

3	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											870
1	143	142	141	2	6	19	125	124	123	20	24	870	
138	8	136	9	11	133	120	26	118	27	29	115	870	
132	131	15	16	128	13	114	113	33	34	110	31	870	
18	14	129	130	17	127	36	32	111	112	35	109	870	
7	134	10	135	137	12	25	116	28	117	119	30	870	
139	5	3	4	140	144	121	23	21	22	122	126	870	
55	89	88	87	56	60	37	107	106	105	38	42	870	
84	62	82	63	65	79	102	44	100	45	47	97	870	
78	77	69	70	74	67	96	95	51	52	92	49	870	
72	68	75	76	71	73	54	50	93	94	53	91	870	
61	80	64	81	83	66	43	98	46	99	101	48	870	
85	59	57	58	86	90	103	41	39	40	104	108	870	
870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	

It is a magic square of order 12, where the four blocks of order 6 are magic squares of equal magic sums.

Example 2.4. Let's consider a magic square of order 12

4	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											870
134	143	3	141	5	1	22	124	20	126	18	133	870	
16	113	108	38	106	40	36	26	120	24	114	129	870	
15	35	48	42	102	104	91	53	93	47	110	130	870	
131	111	45	86	84	57	90	58	60	100	34	14	870	
132	33	46	56	71	76	65	78	89	99	112	13	870	
139	118	51	62	66	77	72	75	83	94	27	6	870	
128	23	101	64	80	67	74	69	81	44	122	17	870	
10	115	96	82	73	70	79	68	63	49	30	135	870	
9	29	95	85	61	88	55	87	59	50	116	136	870	
137	117	98	103	43	41	54	92	52	97	28	8	870	
7	31	37	107	39	105	109	119	25	121	32	138	870	
12	2	142	4	140	144	123	21	125	19	127	11	870	
870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	

It is a well-known **single-digit bordered** magic square. The inner blocks are magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8 and 10.

Example 2.5. Let's consider a magic square of order 12

5	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											870
66	67	77	80	86	59	54	91	23	122	134	11	870	
79	76	70	65	64	81	41	104	118	27	18	127	870	
74	69	75	72	58	87	97	48	106	39	9	136	870	
71	78	68	73	83	62	44	101	28	117	141	4	870	
55	82	61	60	88	89	98	47	121	24	126	19	870	
90	63	84	85	56	57	100	45	31	114	140	5	870	
103	92	99	43	49	93	51	50	38	107	123	22	870	
42	53	46	102	96	52	95	94	120	25	135	10	870	
26	40	30	36	112	34	110	116	108	113	21	124	870	
119	105	115	109	33	111	35	29	32	37	14	131	870	
1	143	128	137	133	16	130	7	20	13	3	139	870	
144	2	17	8	12	129	15	138	125	132	6	142	870	
870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	

It is a **cornered** magic squares, where in each case the magic rectangles of orders 2×4 , 2×6 , 2×8 and 2×10 are of equal sums in each case. It contains magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8 and 10 in the upper left corner.

Example 2.6. Let's consider a magic square of order 12

6	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											870
4	1	143	142	5	139	138	8	9	12	134	135	870	
141	144	2	3	140	6	7	137	136	133	11	10	870	
37	108	43	41	103	101	100	98	48	46	13	132	870	
107	38	102	104	42	44	45	47	97	99	131	14	870	
106	39	57	88	71	76	65	78	61	84	130	15	870	
40	105	60	85	66	77	72	75	64	81	16	129	870	
33	112	87	58	80	67	74	69	83	62	17	128	870	
111	34	86	59	73	70	79	68	82	63	127	18	870	
110	35	93	95	49	51	56	54	90	92	126	19	870	
36	109	52	50	96	94	89	91	55	53	20	125	870	
115	114	32	29	25	119	118	28	122	123	21	24	870	
30	31	113	116	120	26	27	117	23	22	124	121	870	
870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	

It is a **double-digit bordered** magic squares where the magic rectangles of order 2×4 and 2×8 are of equal sums in each case. It contains magic squares of orders 4 and 8.

For more details on these kind of magic squares refer author's work [24, 25, 26, 27].

3 Reduced Entries Magic Squares of Order 12

Below are four examples of reduced entries magic squares of order 12.

Result 3.1. Let's consider following magic square of order 12 with **reduced entries**:

$(R-T)/2-A50$	A52	$(R-T)/2-A43$	$(R-T)/2-A44$	$(R-T)/2-A45$	$(R-T)/2-A46$	$3*(T-R)/2+A43$ $+A44+A45+A46+A47$ $+A48+A49$	$(R-T)/2-A47$	$(R-T)/2-A48$	$(R-T)/2-A49$	$3*T-2*R+A42-$ A52+A50	$(R-T)/2-A42$
A51	A50	A43	A44	A45	A46	$2*(R-T)-A43-A44-A45-$ A46-A47 -A48-A49	A47	A48	A49	A42	$2*T-R-A51-A50-$ A42
$(R-T)/2-A53$	A53	A19	a35	T-M-A16-A17- A18	A16	A17	A18	$A19-A20+2*M$ $+A24-T$	T-M-A24- $2*A19$	A35	$(R-T)/2-A35$
$(R-T)/2-A54$	A54	$2*A14+A25+A15+$ $2*A19-T+M-A20$	T-M- $2*A19-A14$	$A16+A17+A18-$ $(T-M)/2$	$(T-M)/2-A16$	$(T-M)/2-A17$	$(T-M)/2-A18$	T-M-A24-A14- A25-A19+A20	$2*M-T+A19$ $+A24-A15$	A36	$(R-T)/2-A36$
$(R-T)/2-A55$	A55	T-M-A8-A9-A10	$A8+A9+A10-(T-$ M)/2	A1	$A4+M-A6-A1$	$A6-A3-A4$	A3	$A11+A12+A13-(T-$ M)/2	T-M-A11-A12- A13	A37	$(R-T)/2-A37$
$(R-T)/2-A56$	A56	A8	$(T-M)/2-A8$	A6	A4	A5	$M-A4-A5-A6$	$(T-M)/2-A11$	A11	A38	$(R-T)/2-A38$
$3*(T-R)/2+A53+$ A54+A55+A56+ A57+A58+A59	$2*(R-T)-A53-A54-$ A55-A56-A57 - A58-A59	A9	$(T-M)/2-A9$	$A2+A3-A6$	$A1+A2-A5$	$M-A1-A2-A4$	$A4+A5+A6-A2-A3$	$(T-M)/2-A12$	A12	$2*(R-T)-A35-A36 -$ A37-A38-A39 - A40-A41	$3*(T-R)/2+A35$ $+A36+A37+A38+$ A39+A40+A41
$(R-T)/2-A57$	A57	A10	$(T-M)/2-A10$	$M-A1-A2-A3$	$A5-A2-2*A4+A6$	$A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-$ A6	A2	$(T-M)/2-A13$	A13	A39	$(R-T)/2-A39$
$(R-T)/2-A58$	A58	$T-2*A14-A15+A20-$ $3*A19-A24-A25$	$A24+3*A19+A25-$ A20+A14-T+M	$A21+A22+A23-$ $(T-M)/2$	$(T-M)/2-A21$	$(T-M)/2-A22$	$(T-M)/2-A23$	A14	A15	A40	$(R-T)/2-A40$
$(R-T)/2-A59$	A59	A24	$M-A25-A24-A19$	T-M-A21-A22- A23	A21	A22	A23	A25	A19	A41	$(R-T)/2-A41$
$2*T-R-A42-A34-$ A51	R-T-A42-A50-A34	A27	A28	A29	A30	$2*(R-T)-A27-A28-A29-$ A30-A31-A32-A33	A31	A32	A33	A34	T-R+ $2*A42$ $+A50+A34+A51$
$(T-R)/2+A42$ $+A50+A34$	$3*T-2*R+A42$ $+A34-A52$	$(R-T)/2-A27$	$(R-T)/2-A28$	$(R-T)/2-A29$	$(R-T)/2-A30$	$3*(T-R)/2+A27$ $+A28$ $+A29+A30$ $+A31+A32+A33$	$(R-T)/2-A31$	$(R-T)/2-A32$	$(R-T)/2-A33$	$R-T-2*A42+A52-$ A50-A34	$(R-T)/2-A34$

Explanations:

It is a **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 12 embedded with **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 8. The internal magic square is of order 4. The magic rectangles of orders 2×4 and 2×8 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters M, T and R represents the magic squares of orders 4, 8 and 12. In order to avoid decimal entries, the magic sums T and R should be of same type, i.e., either even or odd.

Result 3.2. Let's consider following magic square of order 12 with **reduced entries**:

A1	A4+M-A6-A1	A6-A3-A4	A3	S-M-A10	A10	a18	T-S-A18	L-T-A30	A30	A46	R-L-A46
A6	A4	A5	M-A4-A5-A6	S-M-A11	A11	a19	T-S-A19	L-T-A31	A31	A47	R-L-A47
A2+A3-A6	A1+A2-A5	M-A1-A2-A4	A4+A5+A6-A2-A3	M-S+A10+A11+A12	2*(S-M)-A10-A11-A12	A20	T-S-A20	L-T-A32	A32	A48	R-L-A48
M-A1-A2-A3	A5-A2-2*A4+A6	A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6	A2	S-M-A12	A12	3*(T-S)-A18-A19-A20-A21-A22	2*(S-T)+A18+A19+A20+A21+A22	L-T-A33	A33	A49	R-L-A49
2*S-3*M+A1-A8+3*A4-A11+A10	S-M-A8	3*M-2*S-A1+2*A8-3*A4+A11-A10+A9	S-M-A9	(S-M)/2	(5*M-3*S)/2	A21	T-S-A21	3*(T-L)+A30+A31+A32+A33+A34+A35+A36	4*(L-T)-A30-A31-A32-A33-A34-A35-A36	5*(R-L)-A46-A47-A48-A49-A50-A51-A52-A53-A54	4*(L-R)+A46+A47+A48+A49+A50+A51+A52+A53+A54
2*M-S-A1+A8-3*A4+A11-A10	A8	3*S-4*M+A1-2*A8+3*A4-A11+A10-A9	A9	(5*M-3*S)/2	(S-M)/2	A22	T-S-A22	L-T-A34	A34	A50	R-L-A50
A14	2*A11-T-5*S-A1+2*A9+2*A8+2*A12+A14-3*A4+A18-A19+8*M	A15	4*T+2*S-2*A14+A1-2*A11-2*A9-2*A8-2*A12+3*A4-A18+A19-8*M-A15-A16-A17	A16	A17	(T-S)/2	(7*S-5*T)/2	L-T-A35	A35	A51	R-L-A51
T-S-A14	2*T+4*S+A1-2*A11-2*A9-2*A8-2*A12-A14+3*A4-A18+A19-8*M	T-S-A15	2*A14-3*S-3*T-A1+2*A11+2*A9+2*A8+2*A12-3*A4+A18-A19+8*M+A15+A16+A17	T-S-A16	T-S-A17	(7*S-5*T)/2	(T-S)/2	L-T-A36	A36	A52	R-L-A52
2*L+6*T-6*S-2*A20-A16-2*A15-2*A11-2*A9-A17-2*A8-A22-2*A12-A21-2*A14+3*A4-2*A18+A1-A24+A30-A31-3*M	L-T-A24	L-T-A25	L-T-A26	L-T-A27	6*S-4*L-4*T+2*A20+A29+A27+A16+2*A15+2*A11+2*A9+A17+2*A8+A25+A28+A22+A26-A1+2*A12+A21+2*A14-3*A4+2*A18+2*A24-A30+A31+3*M	L-T-A28	L-T-A29	(L-T)/2	(9*T-7*L)/2	A53	R-L-A53
6*S-L-7*T+2*A20+A16+2*A15+2*A11+2*A9+A17+2*A8+A22+2*A12+A21+2*A14-3*A4+2*A18-A1+A24-A30+A31+3*M	A24	A25	A26	A27	5*L+3*T-6*S-2*A20-A29-A27-A16-2*A15-2*A11-2*A9-A17-2*A8-A25-A28-A22-A26+A1-2*A12-A21-2*A14+3*A4-2*A18-2*A24+A30-A31-3*M	A28	A29	(9*T-7*L)/2	(L-T)/2	A54	R-L-A54
A38	A38-R-A25+A26+2*S+A16-A17-A22+A21+A33-A32-A47+A46	A39	A40	6*R-5*L-2*A38+A25-A26-2*S-A16+A17+A22-A21-A33+A32+A47-A46-A39-A40-A41-A42-A43-A44-A45	A41	A42	A43	A44	A45	(R-L)/2	(11*L-9*R)/2
R-L-A38	2*R-L-A38+A25-A26-2*S-A16+A17+A22-A21-A33+A32+A47-A46	R-L-A39	R-L-A40	4*L-5*R+2*A38-A25+A26+2*S+A16-A17-A22+A21+A33-A32-A47+A46+A39+A40+A41+A42+A43+A44+A45	R-L-A41	R-L-A42	R-L-A43	R-L-A44	R-L-A45	(11*L-9*R)/2	(R-L)/2

Explanations:

It is a **cornered** magic square of order 12, where the magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8 and 10 are in the left upper corner. The magic rectangles of orders 2×4 , 2×6 , 2×8 and 2×10 are of equal width and length for each case. The letters M, S, T, L and R represents the magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8, 10 and 12 respectively. In order to avoid decimal entries, the magic sums S, T, L and R should be of same type, i.e., either even or odd.

Result 3.3. Let's consider following magic square of order 12 with **reduced entries**:

A18	A19	$2*(T-S)/2-A15-A16-A17$	A15	A16	A17	$2*S-T+A18-A19+A23$	$2*(T-S)/2-A23-2*A18$	L-T-A28	A28	A49	R-L-A49
$2*A13+A24+A14+2*A18-2*(T-S)/2-A19$	$2*(T-S)/2-2*A18-A13$	$A15+A16+A17-(T-S)/2$	$(T-S)/2-A15$	$(T-S)/2-A16$	$(T-S)/2-A17$	$2*(T-S)/2-A23-A13-A24-A18+A19$	$2*S-T+A18+A23-A14$	L-T-A29	A29	A50	R-L-A50
$2*(T-S)/2-A7-A8-A9$	$A7+A8+A9-(T-S)/2$	A1	$A4+S-A6-A1$	$A6-A3-A4$	A3	$A10+A11+A12-(T-S)/2$	$2*(T-S)/2-A10-A11-A12$	$A28+A29+A30+A31+A32+A33+A34+3*T-3*L$	$4*L-A28-A29-A30-A31-A32-A33-A34-4*T$	A51	R-L-A51
A7	$(T-S)/2-A7$	A6	A4	A5	$S-A4-A5-A6$	$(T-S)/2-A10$	A10	L-T-A30	A30	A52	R-L-A52
A8	$(T-S)/2-A8$	$A2+A3-A6$	$A1+A2-A5$	$S-A1-A2-A4$	$A4+A5+A6-A2-A3$	$(T-S)/2-A11$	A11	L-T-A31	A31	$5*(R-L)-A49-A50-A51-A52-A53-A54-A55-A56-A57$	$4*(L-R)+A49+A50+A51+A52+A53+A54+A55+A56+A57$
A9	$(T-S)/2-A9$	$S-A1-A2-A3$	$A5-A2-2*A4+A6$	$A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6$	A2	$(T-S)/2-A12$	A12	L-T-A32	A32	A53	R-L-A53
$T-2*A13-A14+A19-3*A18-A23-A24$	$A23+3*A18+A24-A19+A13-2*(T-S)/2$	$A20+A21+A22-(T-S)/2$	$(T-S)/2-A20$	$(T-S)/2-A21$	$(T-S)/2-A22$	A13	A14	L-T-A33	A33	A54	R-L-A54
A23	$T-A23-A18-2*(T-S)/2-A24$	$2*(T-S)/2-A20-A21-A22$	A20	A21	A22	A24	A18	L-T-A34	A34	A55	R-L-A55
L-T-A35	$T-A1+A29-A28+A11+A21+A22+2*A20-6*(T-S)/2-A35+2*A10+A12-3*A4$	$T+A1-A29+A28-A11-A21-A22-2*A20+6*(T-S)/2+2*A35-2*A10-A12-2*L+3*A4+A36+A37+A38+A39+A40$	L-T-A36	L-T-A37	L-T-A38	L-T-A39	L-T-A40	$(L-T)/2$	$(9*T-7*L)/2$	A56	R-L-A56
A35	$A1-A29+A28-A11-A21-A22-2*A20+6*(T-S)/2+A35-2*T-2*A10-A12+L+3*A4$	$3*L-2*T-A1+A29-A28+A11+A21+A22+2*A20-6*(T-S)/2-2*A35+2*A10+A12-3*A4-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40$	A36	A37	A38	A39	A40	$(9*T-7*L)/2$	$(L-T)/2$	A57	R-L-A57
$7*L-2*A28-A32+R+2*A11-8*T-2*A35+2*A21-A38-A39-A40-2*A36-A37-3*A4+2*A10-4*(T-S)/2-A31+2*A20-A34-A33-2*A30-A1-A49+A50+A41$	A41	A42	A43	$2*A28-12*L+A32+4*R-2*A11+8*T+2*A35-2*A21+A38+A39+A40+2*A36+A37+3*A4-2*A10+4*(T-S)/2+A31-2*A20+A34+A33+2*A30+A49-A50-A47-A48+A1-A46-A45-A44-A43-A42-2*A41$	A44	A45	A46	A47	A48	$(R-L)/2$	$(11*L-9*R)/2$
$2*A28-8*L+A32-2*A11+8*T+2*A35-2*A21+A38+A39+A40+2*A36+A37+3*A4-2*A10+4*(T-S)/2+A31-2*A20+A34+A33-2*A30+A49+A50+A47+A48-A1+A46+A45+A44+A43+A42+2*A41$	R-L-A41	R-L-A42	R-L-A43	$11*L-2*A28-A32-3*R+2*A11-8*T-2*A35+2*A21-A38-A39-A40-2*A36-A37-3*A4+2*A10-4*(T-S)/2-A31+2*A20-A34-A33-2*A30-A49+A50+A47+A48-A1+A46+A45+A44+A43+A42+2*A41$	R-L-A44	R-L-A45	R-L-A46	R-L-A47	R-L-A48	$(11*L-9*R)/2$	$(R-L)/2$

Explanations:

It is a **cornered** magic square of order 12 with **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 8 at the upper left corner embedded with a magic square of order 4. The four magic rectangles of orders 2×4 are of equal width and length. Also the magic rectangles of orders 2×8 and 2×10 are of equal width and length in each case. It also contains a magic square of order 10. The letters S, T, L and R represents the magic squares of orders 4, 8, 10 and 12 respectively. In order to avoid decimal entries, the magic sums T, L and R should be of same type, i.e., either even or odd.

Result 3.4. Let's consider following magic squares of order 12 with **reduced entries**:

$2*(T-S)/2-A35-A20-A41$	$2*A41+A35+A34+A20-A21-2*A28+T-5*(T-S)/2-A27$	A15	A16	A17	A18	$3*(T-S)/2-A15-A16-A17-A18-A19$	A19	$A21+2*A28-A20+A27-A41-A34$	A20	A50	R-T-A50
A27	A28	$(T-S)/2-A15$	$(T-S)/2-A16$	$(T-S)/2-A17$	$(T-S)/2-A18$	$A15+A16+A17+A18+A19-T+S$	$(T-S)/2-A19$	$T-A27-A28-3*(T-S)/2-A21$	A21	A51	R-T-A51
$3*(T-S)/2-A22-A23-A24-A25-A26$	$A22+A23+A24+A25+A26-2*(T-S)/2$	A1	$A4+M-A6-A1$	$A6-A3-A4$	A3	S-M-A10	A10	$(T-S)/2-A29$	A29	A52	R-T-A52
A22	$(T-S)/2-A22$	A6	A4	A5	$M-A4-A5-A6$	$A10+A11+A12-S+M$	$2*(S-M)-A10-A11-A12$	$(T-S)/2-A30$	A30	A53	R-T-A53
A23	$(T-S)/2-A23$	$A2+A3-A6$	$A1+A2-A5$	$M-A1-A2-A4$	$A4+A5+A6-A2-A3$	S-M-A11	A11	$A29+A30+A31+A32+A33-T+S$	$3*(T-S)/2-A29-A30-A31-A32-A33$	$5*(R-T)-A50-A51-A52-A53-A54-A55-A56-A57-A58$	$4*(T-R)+A50+A51+A52+A53+A54+A55+A56+A57+A58$
A24	$(T-S)/2-A24$	$M-A1-A2-A3$	$A5-A2-2*A4+A6$	$A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6$	A2	S-M-A12	A12	$(T-S)/2-A31$	A31	A54	R-T-A54
A25	$(T-S)/2-A25$	S-M-A8	$2*S-A8-A1-3*A4-2*A10-A11-A12-M$	$2*A8+A1+A9+3*A4+2*A10+A11+A12+M-2*S$	S-M-A9	$(S-M)/2$	$(5*M-3*S)/2$	$(T-S)/2-A32$	A32	A55	R-T-A55
A26	$(T-S)/2-A26$	A8	$A8+A1+3*A4+2*A10+A11+A12-S$	$3*S-2*A8-A1-A9-3*A4-2*A10-A11-A12-2*M$	A9	$(5*M-3*S)/2$	$(S-M)/2$	$(T-S)/2-A33$	A33	A56	R-T-A56
$T-5*(T-S)/2+A35+A20-A27$	$5*(T-S)/2-T-A20+A27+A28-A41+A21$	$(T-S)/2-A36$	$A36+A37+A38+A39+A40-2*(T-S)/2$	$(T-S)/2-A37$	$(T-S)/2-A38$	$(T-S)/2-A39$	$(T-S)/2-A40$	$A41+A20-A28$	$T-A20-A21-3*(T-S)/2-A35$	A57	R-T-A57
A41	$T-3*(T-S)/2-A41-A35-A34$	A36	$3*(T-S)/2-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40$	A37	A38	A39	A40	A34	A35	A58	R-T-A58
$(11*S-5*T)/2-2*A12-4*M+A38+A39+A40+2*A36+A37-3*A4-2*A10+R-A30+A29-A1-A50+A51-2*A8-2*A9+A42$	A42	A43	A44	$2*A12-(11*S+5*T)/2+4*M-A38-A39-A40-2*A36-A37+3*A4+2*A10+4*R+A30-A29+A50-A51+2*A8+2*A9-A48-A49+A1-A47-A46-A45-A44-A43-2*A42$	A45	A46	A47	A48	A49	$(R-T)/2$	$(11*T-9*R)/2$
$(3*T-11*S)/2+2*A12+4*M-A38-A39-A40-2*A36-A37+3*A4+2*A10+A30-A29+A1+A50-A51+2*A8+2*A9-A42$	R-T-A42	R-T-A43	R-T-A44	$(11*S+3*T)/2-2*A12-4*M+A38+A39+A40+2*A36+A37-3*A4-2*A10-3*R-A30+A29-A50+A51-2*A8-2*A9+A48+A49-A1+A47+A46+A45+A44+A43+2*A42$	R-T-A45	R-T-A46	R-T-A47	R-T-A48	R-T-A49	$(11*T-9*R)/2$	$(R-T)/2$

Explanations:

It is also a **cornered** magic square of order 12 with **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 10 at the upper left corner embedded with a **cornered** magic square of order 6 containing magic square of order 4. The magic rectangles of orders 2×4 , 2×6 and 2×10 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters M, S, T and R represents the magic squares of orders 4, 6, 10 and 12 respectively. In order to avoid decimal entries, the magic sums S, T and R should be of same type, i.e., either even or odd.

Actually there are 13 different types of representing reduced entries magic squares of order 12. Here we have considered only four. For other types refer author's work [36]. The examples given in the next section are based on the Results 3.1 to 3.4, where the few entries represents **dates** in two different ways, and the **magic sums** are the respective **days** of the year 2025.

4 Days and Dates of the Year 2025 for the Month July

This work brings **dates** and **days of the year**, 2025 in terms of magic squares of order 12. This section is only for the month **July, 2025**. As explained above, here there are four types of magic squares of order 12 based on the Results 3.1 to 3.4. The readers can see the complete work as **pdf files** for the months of **October** and **December 2025** at the author's web-site link <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=16068>.

■ 182nd Day of the Year - 01.07.2025

1	mgc	12x12	Inder J. Taneja	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	182	1	mgc	12x12	Inder J. Taneja	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	182
	-44	62	-37	-38	-39	-40	344	-41	-42	-43	136	-36	182
	61	60	53	54	55	56	-328	57	58	59	52	-55	182
	-47	63	29	30	-21	26	27	28	63	-32	45	-29	182
	-48	64	76	-22	51	4	3	2	-32	68	46	-30	182
	-49	65	3	27	1	93	-11	7	36	-6	47	-31	182
	-50	66	18	12	16	20	25	29	9	21	48	-32	182
	414	-398	19	11	13	-2	47	32	8	22	-272	288	182
	-51	67	20	10	60	-21	29	22	7	23	49	-33	182
	-52	68	-49	90	66	-1	-2	-3	24	25	50	-34	182
	-53	69	34	-8	-36	31	32	33	35	29	51	-35	182
	-39	-124	107	38	39	40	-2268	41	42	2025	44	237	182
	140	120	-91	-22	-23	-24	2284	-25	-26	-2009	-114	-28	182
	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182
	1	63	-1	7	0	30	38	-18	-20	50	66	-34	182
	26	20	25	-1	-1	31	39	-19	-21	51	67	-35	182
	3	-2	27	42	63	-33	40	-20	-22	52	68	-36	182
	40	-11	19	22	-2	32	-140	160	-23	53	69	-37	182
	22	2	35	1	15	25	41	-21	281	-251	-470	502	182
	8	28	-5	29	25	15	42	-22	-24	54	70	-38	182
	34	152	35	-234	36	37	10	50	-25	55	71	-39	182
	-14	-132	-15	254	-16	-17	50	10	-26	56	72	-40	182
	-464	-14	-15	-77	-1995	2722	-18	-19	15	15	73	-41	182
	494	44	45	107	2025	-2692	48	49	15	15	74	-42	182
	58	136	59	60	-468	61	62	63	64	65	16	6	182
	-26	-104	-27	-28	500	-29	-30	-31	-32	-33	6	16	182
	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182
	38	39	-48	35	36	37	32	-59	-8	48	69	-37	182
	121	-49	78	-5	-6	-7	-59	37	-9	49	70	-38	182
	-24	54	1	43	-1	7	63	-33	237	-197	71	-39	182
	27	3	26	20	25	-21	0	30	-10	50	72	-40	182
	28	2	3	-2	7	42	-1	31	-11	51	-497	529	182
	29	1	20	-11	19	22	-2	32	-12	52	73	-41	182
	-152	135	93	-10	-11	-12	33	34	-13	53	74	-42	182
	43	-75	-63	40	41	42	44	38	-14	54	75	-43	182
	-67	49	2233	-16	-17	-18	-19	-1985	20	-30	76	-44	182
	107	-9	-2193	56	57	58	59	2025	-30	20	77	-45	182
	-2414	61	62	63	2058	64	65	66	67	68	16	6	182
	2446	-29	-30	-31	-2026	-32	-33	-34	-35	-36	6	16	182
	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182
	-86	127	25	26	27	28	-75	29	19	30	60	-28	182
	37	38	-5	-6	-7	-8	95	-9	-16	31	61	-29	182
	-110	130	1	83	-11	7	10	20	-19	39	62	-30	182
	32	-12	16	20	25	19	33	-3	-20	40	63	-31	182
	33	-13	13	-2	37	32	9	21	165	-145	-416	448	182
	34	-14	50	-21	29	22	8	22	-21	41	64	-32	182
	35	-15	12	-22	59	11	15	35	-22	42	65	-33	182
	36	-16	18	52	-29	19	35	15	-23	43	66	-34	182
	88	-25	-26	200	-27	-28	-29	-30	43	-16	67	-35	182
	51	-50	46	-180	47	48	49	50	44	45	68	-36	182
	266	107	53	54	-2572	55	56	57	2025	59	16	6	182
	-234	-75	-21	-22	2604	-23	-24	-25	-1993	-27	6	16	182
	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182

■ 183rd Day of the Year - 02.07.2025

2	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											183													
-44	62	-37	-38	-39	-40	344	-41	-42	-43	137	-36	183	2	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											183
61	60	53	54	55	56	-328	57	58	59	52	-54	183	26	63	-1	7	0	30	38	-18	-20	50	66	-34	183	
-47	63	29	30	-21	26	27	28	64	-32	45	-29	183	3	-1	27	42	63	-33	40	-20	-22	52	68	-36	183	
-48	64	76	-22	51	4	3	2	-32	69	46	-30	183	40	-11	20	22	-2	32	-140	160	-23	53	69	-37	183	
-49	65	3	27	2	93	-11	7	36	-6	47	-31	183	22	2	35	1	15	26	41	-21	281	-251	-470	502	183	
-50	66	18	12	16	20	25	30	9	21	48	-32	183	8	28	-5	29	26	15	42	-22	-24	54	70	-38	183	
414	-398	19	11	13	-1	47	32	8	22	-272	288	183	34	153	35	-235	36	37	10	51	-25	55	71	-39	183	
-51	67	20	10	60	-21	30	22	7	23	49	-33	183	-14	-133	-15	255	-16	-17	51	10	-26	56	72	-40	183	
-52	68	-48	90	66	-1	-2	-3	24	25	50	-34	183	-464	-14	-15	-177	-1995	2822	-18	-19	15	16	73	-41	183	
-53	69	34	-7	-36	31	32	33	35	29	51	-35	183	494	44	45	207	2025	-2792	48	49	16	15	74	-42	183	
-38	-124	207	38	39	40	-2368	41	42	2025	44	237	183	58	237	59	60	-569	61	62	63	64	65	16	7	183	
140	121	-191	-22	-23	-24	2384	-25	-26	-2009	-114	-28	183	-26	-205	-27	-28	601	-29	-30	-31	-32	-33	7	16	183	
183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	

2	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											183													
38	39	-48	35	36	37	33	-59	-8	48	69	-37	183	2	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											183
121	-49	78	-5	-6	-7	-59	38	-9	49	70	-38	183	-86	128	25	26	27	28	-75	29	19	30	60	-28	183	
-24	54	2	43	-1	7	63	-33	237	-197	71	-39	183	37	38	-5	-6	-7	-8	95	-9	-15	31	61	-29	183	
27	3	26	20	25	-20	0	30	-10	50	72	-40	183	-110	130	2	83	-11	7	10	20	-19	39	62	-30	183	
28	2	3	-1	7	42	-1	31	-11	51	-497	529	183	32	-12	16	20	25	20	33	-3	-20	40	63	-31	183	
29	1	20	-11	20	22	-2	32	-12	52	73	-41	183	33	-13	13	-1	37	32	9	21	165	-145	-416	448	183	
-151	135	93	-10	-11	-12	33	34	-13	53	74	-42	183	34	-14	50	-21	30	22	8	22	-21	41	64	-32	183	
43	-74	-63	40	41	42	44	38	-14	54	75	-43	183	35	-15	12	-22	59	11	15	36	-22	42	65	-33	183	
-167	-51	2433	-16	-17	-18	-19	-1985	20	-29	76	-44	183	36	-16	18	52	-29	19	36	15	-23	43	66	-34	183	
207	91	-2393	56	57	58	59	2025	-29	20	77	-45	183	89	-26	-26	200	-27	-28	-29	-30	43	-15	67	-35	183	
-2615	61	62	63	2259	64	65	66	67	68	16	7	183	51	-49	46	-180	47	48	49	50	44	45	68	-36	183	
2647	-29	-30	-31	-2227	-32	-33	-34	-35	-36	7	16	183	365	207	53	54	-2771	55	56	57	2025	59	16	7	183	
183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	-333	-175	-21	-22	2803	-23	-24	-25	-1993	-27	7	16	183	
183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	183	

■ 184th Day of the Year - 03.07.2025

3	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										184	3	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										184		
	-43	62	-36	-37	-38	-39	341	-40	-41	-42	132	-35	184		3	61	-1	7	0	30	38	-18	-20	50	66	-32	184
	61	60	53	54	55	56	-324	57	58	59	52	-57	184		26	20	25	-1	-1	31	39	-19	-21	51	67	-33	184
	-46	63	29	30	-21	26	27	28	63	-32	45	-28	184		3	0	25	42	63	-33	40	-20	-22	52	68	-34	184
	-47	64	76	-22	51	4	3	2	-32	68	46	-29	184		38	-11	21	22	-2	32	-140	160	-23	53	69	-35	184
	-48	65	3	27	3	91	-11	7	36	-6	47	-30	184		24	2	33	1	15	25	41	-21	281	-251	-460	494	184
	-49	66	18	12	16	20	25	29	9	21	48	-31	184		6	28	-3	29	25	15	42	-22	-24	54	70	-36	184
	411	-394	19	11	13	0	45	32	8	22	-268	285	184		34	150	35	-232	36	37	10	50	-25	55	71	-37	184
	-50	67	20	10	58	-21	31	22	7	23	49	-32	184		-14	-130	-15	252	-16	-17	50	10	-26	56	72	-38	184
	-51	68	-49	90	66	-1	-2	-3	24	25	50	-33	184		-462	-14	-15	-277	-1995	2920	-18	-19	15	15	73	-39	184
	-52	69	34	-8	-36	31	32	33	35	29	51	-34	184		492	44	45	307	2025	-2890	48	49	15	15	74	-40	184
	-41	-122	307	38	39	40	-2464	41	42	2025	44	235	184		58	334	59	60	-656	61	62	63	64	65	17	-3	184
	139	116	-290	-21	-22	-23	2481	-24	-25	-2008	-112	-27	184		-24	-300	-25	-26	690	-27	-28	-29	-30	-31	-3	17	184
	184	184	184	184	184	184	184	184	184	184	184	184	184		184	184	184	184	184	184	184	184	184	184	184	184	184

3	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										184	3	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										184		
	38	39	-48	35	36	37	32	-59	-8	48	69	-35	184		-86	127	25	26	27	28	-75	29	19	30	60	-26	184
	121	-49	78	-5	-6	-7	-59	37	-9	49	70	-36	184		37	38	-5	-6	-7	-8	95	-9	-16	31	61	-27	184
	-24	54	3	41	-1	7	63	-33	237	-197	71	-37	184		-110	130	3	81	-11	7	10	20	-19	39	62	-28	184
	27	3	26	20	25	-21	0	30	-10	50	72	-38	184		32	-12	16	20	25	19	33	-3	-20	40	63	-29	184
	28	2	3	0	5	42	-1	31	-11	51	-487	521	184		33	-13	13	0	35	32	9	21	165	-145	-406	440	184
	29	1	18	-11	21	22	-2	32	-12	52	73	-39	184		34	-14	48	-21	31	22	8	22	-21	41	64	-30	184
	-152	135	93	-10	-11	-12	33	34	-13	53	74	-40	184		35	-15	12	-24	61	11	15	35	-22	42	65	-31	184
	43	-75	-63	40	41	42	44	38	-14	54	75	-41	184		36	-16	18	54	-31	19	35	15	-23	43	66	-32	184
	-267	-153	2635	-16	-17	-18	-19	-1985	20	-30	76	-42	184		88	-25	-26	200	-27	-28	-29	-30	43	-16	67	-33	184
	307	193	-2595	56	57	58	59	2025	-30	20	77	-43	184		51	-50	46	-180	47	48	49	50	44	45	68	-34	184
	-2814	61	62	63	2468	64	65	66	67	68	17	-3	184		466	307	53	54	-2962	55	56	57	2025	59	17	-3	184
	2848	-27	-28	-29	-2434	-30	-31	-32	-33	-34	-3	17	184		-432	-273	-19	-20	2996	-21	-22	-23	-1991	-25	-3	17	184
	184	184	184	184	184	184	184	184	184	184	184	184	184		184	184	184	184	184	184	184	184	184	184	184	184	184

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4	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											185													
-43	62	-36	-37	-38	-39	341	-40	-41	-42	133	-35	185	4	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											185
61	60	53	54	55	56	-324	57	58	59	52	-56	185	4	61	-1	7	0	30	38	-18	-20	50	66	-32	185	
-46	63	29	30	-21	26	27	28	64	-32	45	-28	185	26	20	25	0	-1	31	39	-19	-21	51	67	-33	185	
-47	64	76	-22	51	4	3	2	-32	69	46	-29	185	3	1	25	42	63	-33	40	-20	-22	52	68	-34	185	
-48	65	3	27	4	91	-11	7	36	-6	47	-30	185	38	-11	22	22	-2	32	-140	160	-23	53	69	-35	185	
-49	66	18	12	16	20	25	30	9	21	48	-31	185	24	2	33	1	15	26	41	-21	281	-251	-460	494	185	
411	-394	19	11	13	1	45	32	8	22	-268	285	185	6	28	-3	29	26	15	42	-22	-24	54	70	-36	185	
-50	67	20	10	58	-21	32	22	7	23	49	-32	185	34	151	35	-233	36	37	10	51	-25	55	71	-37	185	
-51	68	-48	90	66	-1	-2	-3	24	25	50	-33	185	-14	-131	-15	253	-16	-17	51	10	-26	56	72	-38	185	
-52	69	34	-7	-36	31	32	33	35	29	51	-34	185	-462	-14	-15	-377	-1995	3020	-18	-19	15	16	73	-39	185	
-40	-122	407	38	39	40	-2564	41	42	2025	44	235	185	492	44	45	407	2025	-2990	48	49	16	15	74	-40	185	
139	117	-390	-21	-22	-23	2581	-24	-25	-2008	-112	-27	185	58	435	59	60	-757	61	62	63	64	65	17	-2	185	
185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	-24	-401	-25	-26	791	-27	-28	-29	-30	-31	-2	17	185	
185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	

4	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											185													
38	39	-48	35	36	37	33	-59	-8	48	69	-35	185	4	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											185
121	-49	78	-5	-6	-7	-59	38	-9	49	70	-36	185	-86	128	25	26	27	28	-75	29	19	30	60	-26	185	
-24	54	4	41	-1	7	63	-33	237	-197	71	-37	185	37	38	-5	-6	-7	-8	95	-9	-15	31	61	-27	185	
27	3	26	20	25	-20	0	30	-10	50	72	-38	185	-110	130	4	81	-11	7	10	20	-19	39	62	-28	185	
28	2	3	1	5	42	-1	31	-11	51	-487	521	185	32	-12	16	20	25	20	33	-3	-20	40	63	-29	185	
29	1	18	-11	22	22	-2	32	-12	52	73	-39	185	33	-13	13	1	35	32	9	21	165	-145	-406	440	185	
-151	135	93	-10	-11	-12	33	34	-13	53	74	-40	185	34	-14	48	-21	32	22	8	22	-21	41	64	-30	185	
43	-74	-63	40	41	42	44	38	-14	54	75	-41	185	35	-15	12	-24	61	11	15	36	-22	42	65	-31	185	
-367	-253	2835	-16	-17	-18	-19	-1985	20	-29	76	-42	185	36	-16	18	54	-31	19	36	15	-23	43	66	-32	185	
407	293	-2795	56	57	58	59	2025	-29	20	77	-43	185	89	-26	-26	200	-27	-28	-29	-30	43	-15	67	-33	185	
-3015	61	62	63	2669	64	65	66	67	68	17	-2	185	51	-49	46	-180	47	48	49	50	44	45	68	-34	185	
3049	-27	-28	-29	-2635	-30	-31	-32	-33	-34	-2	17	185	565	407	53	54	-3161	55	56	57	2025	59	17	-2	185	
185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	-531	-373	-19	-20	3195	-21	-22	-23	-1991	-25	-2	17	185	
185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	185	

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5	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											186													
-42	62	-35	-36	-37	-38	338	-39	-40	-41	128	-34	186	5	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											186
61	60	53	54	55	56	-320	57	58	59	52	-59	186	5	59	-1	7	0	30	38	-18	-20	50	66	-30	186	
-45	63	29	30	-21	26	27	28	63	-32	45	-27	186	26	20	25	-1	-1	31	39	-19	-21	51	67	-31	186	
-46	64	76	-22	51	4	3	2	-32	68	46	-28	186	3	2	23	42	63	-33	40	-20	-22	52	68	-32	186	
-47	65	3	27	5	89	-11	7	36	-6	47	-29	186	36	-11	23	22	-2	32	-140	160	-23	53	69	-33	186	
-48	66	18	12	16	20	25	29	9	21	48	-30	186	26	2	31	1	15	25	41	-21	281	-251	-450	486	186	
408	-390	19	11	13	2	43	32	8	22	-264	282	186	4	28	-1	29	25	15	42	-22	-24	54	70	-34	186	
-49	67	20	10	56	-21	33	22	7	23	49	-31	186	34	148	35	-230	36	37	10	50	-25	55	71	-35	186	
-50	68	-49	90	66	-1	-2	-3	24	25	50	-32	186	-14	-128	-15	250	-16	-17	50	10	-26	56	72	-36	186	
-51	69	34	-8	-36	31	32	33	35	29	51	-33	186	-460	-14	-15	-477	-1995	3118	-18	-19	15	15	73	-37	186	
-43	-120	507	38	39	40	-2660	41	42	2025	44	233	186	490	44	45	507	2025	-3088	48	49	15	15	74	-38	186	
138	112	-489	-20	-21	-22	2678	-23	-24	-2007	-110	-26	186	58	532	59	60	-844	61	62	63	64	65	18	-12	186	
186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	-22	-496	-23	-24	880	-25	-26	-27	-28	-29	-12	18	186	
186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	

5	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											186													
38	39	-48	35	36	37	32	-59	-8	48	69	-33	186	5 <th>mgc</th> <th colspan="11">12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT</th> <th>186</th>	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											186
121	-49	78	-5	-6	-7	-59	37	-9	49	70	-34	186	-86	127	25	26	27	28	-75	29	19	30	60	-24	186	
-24	54	5	39	-1	7	63	-33	237	-197	71	-35	186	37	38	-5	-6	-7	-8	95	-9	-16	31	61	-25	186	
27	3	26	20	25	-21	0	30	-10	50	72	-36	186	-110	130	5	79	-11	7	10	20	-19	39	62	-26	186	
28	2	3	2	3	42	-1	31	-11	51	-477	513	186	32	-12	16	20	25	19	33	-3	-20	40	63	-27	186	
29	1	16	-11	23	22	-2	32	-12	52	73	-37	186	33	-13	13	2	33	32	9	21	165	-145	-396	432	186	
-152	135	93	-10	-11	-12	33	34	-13	53	74	-38	186	34	-14	46	-21	33	22	8	22	-21	41	64	-28	186	
43	-75	-63	40	41	42	44	38	-14	54	75	-39	186	35	-15	12	-26	63	11	15	35	-22	42	65	-29	186	
-467	-355	3037	-16	-17	-18	-19	-1985	20	-30	76	-40	186	36	-16	18	56	-33	19	35	15	-23	43	66	-30	186	
507	395	-2997	56	57	58	59	2025	-30	20	77	-41	186	88	-25	-26	200	-27	-28	-29	-30	43	-16	67	-31	186	
-3214	61	62	63	2878	64	65	66	67	68	18	-12	186	51	-50	46	-180	47	48	49	50	44	45	68	-32	186	
3250	-25	-26	-27	-2842	-28	-29	-30	-31	-32	-12	18	186	666	507	53	54	-3352	55	56	57	2025	59	18	-12	186	
186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	-630	-471	-17	-18	3388	-19	-20	-21	-1989	-23	-12	18	186	
186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	186	

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6	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										187													
-42	62	-35	-36	-37	-38	338	-39	-40	-41	129	-34	187	6	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										187
61	60	53	54	55	56	-320	57	58	59	52	-58	187	6	59	-1	7	0	30	38	-18	-20	50	66	-30	187
-45	63	29	30	-21	26	27	28	64	-32	45	-27	187	26	20	25	0	-1	31	39	-19	-21	51	67	-31	187
-46	64	76	-22	51	4	3	2	-32	69	46	-28	187	3	3	23	42	63	-33	40	-20	-22	52	68	-32	187
-47	65	3	27	6	89	-11	7	36	-6	47	-29	187	36	-11	24	22	-2	32	-140	160	-23	53	69	-33	187
-48	66	18	12	16	20	25	30	9	21	48	-30	187	26	2	31	1	15	26	41	-21	281	-251	-450	486	187
408	-390	19	11	13	3	43	32	8	22	-264	282	187	4	28	-1	29	26	15	42	-22	-24	54	70	-34	187
-49	67	20	10	56	-21	34	22	7	23	49	-31	187	34	149	35	-231	36	37	10	51	-25	55	71	-35	187
-50	68	-48	90	66	-1	-2	-3	24	25	50	-32	187	-14	-129	-15	251	-16	-17	51	10	-26	56	72	-36	187
-51	69	34	-7	-36	31	32	33	35	29	51	-33	187	-460	-14	-15	-577	-1995	3218	-18	-19	15	16	73	-37	187
-42	-120	607	38	39	40	-2760	41	42	2025	44	233	187	490	44	45	607	2025	-3188	48	49	16	15	74	-38	187
138	113	-589	-20	-21	-22	2778	-23	-24	-2007	-110	-26	187	58	633	59	60	-945	61	62	63	64	65	18	-11	187
187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	-22	-597	-23	-24	981	-25	-26	-27	-28	-29	-11	18	187
187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187

6	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										187													
38	39	-48	35	36	37	33	-59	-8	48	69	-33	187	6	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										187
121	-49	78	-5	-6	-7	-59	38	-9	49	70	-34	187	-86	128	25	26	27	28	-75	29	19	30	60	-24	187
-24	54	6	39	-1	7	63	-33	237	-197	71	-35	187	37	38	-5	-6	-7	-8	95	-9	-15	31	61	-25	187
27	3	26	20	25	-20	0	30	-10	50	72	-36	187	-110	130	6	79	-11	7	10	20	-19	39	62	-26	187
28	2	3	3	3	42	-1	31	-11	51	-477	513	187	32	-12	16	20	25	20	33	-3	-20	40	63	-27	187
29	1	16	-11	24	22	-2	32	-12	52	73	-37	187	33	-13	13	3	33	32	9	21	165	-145	-396	432	187
-151	135	93	-10	-11	-12	33	34	-13	53	74	-38	187	34	-14	46	-21	34	22	8	22	-21	41	64	-28	187
43	-74	-63	40	41	42	44	38	-14	54	75	-39	187	35	-15	12	-26	63	11	15	36	-22	42	65	-29	187
-567	-455	3237	-16	-17	-18	-19	-1985	20	-29	76	-40	187	36	-16	18	56	-33	19	36	15	-23	43	66	-30	187
607	495	-3197	56	57	58	59	2025	-29	20	77	-41	187	89	-26	-26	200	-27	-28	-29	-30	43	-15	67	-31	187
-3415	61	62	63	3079	64	65	66	67	68	18	-11	187	51	-49	46	-180	47	48	49	50	44	45	68	-32	187
3451	-25	-26	-27	-3043	-28	-29	-30	-31	-32	-11	18	187	765	607	53	54	-3551	55	56	57	2025	59	18	-11	187
187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	-729	-571	-17	-18	3587	-19	-20	-21	-1989	-23	-11	18	187
187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187

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7	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											188													
-41	62	-34	-35	-36	-37	335	-38	-39	-40	124	-33	188	7	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											188
61	60	53	54	55	56	-316	57	58	59	52	-61	188	7	57	-1	7	0	30	38	-18	-20	50	66	-28	188	
-44	63	29	30	-21	26	27	28	63	-32	45	-26	188	26	20	25	-1	-1	31	39	-19	-21	51	67	-29	188	
-45	64	76	-22	51	4	3	2	-32	68	46	-27	188	3	4	21	42	63	-33	40	-20	-22	52	68	-30	188	
-46	65	3	27	7	87	-11	7	36	-6	47	-28	188	34	-11	25	22	-2	32	-140	160	-23	53	69	-31	188	
-47	66	18	12	16	20	25	29	9	21	48	-29	188	28	2	29	1	15	25	41	-21	281	-251	-440	478	188	
405	-386	19	11	13	4	41	32	8	22	-260	279	188	2	28	1	29	25	15	42	-22	-24	54	70	-32	188	
-48	67	20	10	54	-21	35	22	7	23	49	-30	188	34	146	35	-228	36	37	10	50	-25	55	71	-33	188	
-49	68	-49	90	66	-1	-2	-3	24	25	50	-31	188	-14	-126	-15	248	-16	-17	50	10	-26	56	72	-34	188	
-50	69	34	-8	-36	31	32	33	35	29	51	-32	188	-458	-14	-15	-677	-1995	3316	-18	-19	15	15	73	-35	188	
-45	-118	707	38	39	40	-2856	41	42	2025	44	231	188	488	44	45	707	2025	-3286	48	49	15	15	74	-36	188	
137	108	-688	-19	-20	-21	2875	-22	-23	-2006	-108	-25	188	58	730	59	60	-1032	61	62	63	64	65	19	-21	188	
188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	-20	-692	-21	-22	1070	-23	-24	-25	-26	-27	-21	19	188	
188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	

7	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											188													
38	39	-48	35	36	37	32	-59	-8	48	69	-31	188	7	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											188
121	-49	78	-5	-6	-7	-59	37	-9	49	70	-32	188	-86	127	25	26	27	28	-75	29	19	30	60	-22	188	
-24	54	7	37	-1	7	63	-33	237	-197	71	-33	188	37	38	-5	-6	-7	-8	95	-9	-16	31	61	-23	188	
27	3	26	20	25	-21	0	30	-10	50	72	-34	188	-110	130	7	77	-11	7	10	20	-19	39	62	-24	188	
28	2	3	4	1	42	-1	31	-11	51	-467	505	188	32	-12	16	20	25	19	33	-3	-20	40	63	-25	188	
29	1	14	-11	25	22	-2	32	-12	52	73	-35	188	33	-13	13	4	31	32	9	21	165	-145	-386	424	188	
-152	135	93	-10	-11	-12	33	34	-13	53	74	-36	188	34	-14	44	-21	35	22	8	22	-21	41	64	-26	188	
43	-75	-63	40	41	42	44	38	-14	54	75	-37	188	35	-15	12	-28	65	11	15	35	-22	42	65	-27	188	
-667	-557	3439	-16	-17	-18	-19	-1985	20	-30	76	-38	188	36	-16	18	58	-35	19	35	15	-23	43	66	-28	188	
707	597	-3399	56	57	58	59	2025	-30	20	77	-39	188	88	-25	-26	200	-27	-28	-29	-30	43	-16	67	-29	188	
-3614	61	62	63	3288	64	65	66	67	68	19	-21	188	51	-50	46	-180	47	48	49	50	44	45	68	-30	188	
3652	-23	-24	-25	-3250	-26	-27	-28	-29	-30	-21	19	188	866	707	53	54	-3742	55	56	57	2025	59	19	-21	188	
188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	-828	-669	-15	-16	3780	-17	-18	-19	-1987	-21	-21	19	188	
188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	188	

■ 189th Day of the Year - 08.07.2025

8	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											189													
-41	62	-34	-35	-36	-37	335	-38	-39	-40	125	-33	189	8	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											189
61	60	53	54	55	56	-316	57	58	59	52	-60	189	8	57	-1	7	0	30	38	-18	-20	50	66	-28	189	
-44	63	29	30	-21	26	27	28	64	-32	45	-26	189	26	20	25	0	-1	31	39	-19	-21	51	67	-29	189	
-45	64	76	-22	51	4	3	2	-32	69	46	-27	189	3	5	21	42	63	-33	40	-20	-22	52	68	-30	189	
-46	65	3	27	8	87	-11	7	36	-6	47	-28	189	34	-11	26	22	-2	32	-140	160	-23	53	69	-31	189	
-47	66	18	12	16	20	25	30	9	21	48	-29	189	28	2	29	1	15	26	41	-21	281	-251	-440	478	189	
405	-386	19	11	13	5	41	32	8	22	-260	279	189	2	28	1	29	26	15	42	-22	-24	54	70	-32	189	
-48	67	20	10	54	-21	36	22	7	23	49	-30	189	34	147	35	-229	36	37	10	51	-25	55	71	-33	189	
-49	68	-48	90	66	-1	-2	-3	24	25	50	-31	189	-14	-127	-15	249	-16	-17	51	10	-26	56	72	-34	189	
-50	69	34	-7	-36	31	32	33	35	29	51	-32	189	-458	-14	-15	-777	-1995	3416	-18	-19	15	16	73	-35	189	
-44	-118	807	38	39	40	-2956	41	42	2025	44	231	189	488	44	45	807	2025	-3386	48	49	16	15	74	-36	189	
137	109	-788	-19	-20	-21	2975	-22	-23	-2006	-108	-25	189	58	831	59	60	-1133	61	62	63	64	65	19	-20	189	
189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	-20	-793	-21	-22	1171	-23	-24	-25	-26	-27	-20	19	189	
189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	

8	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											189													
38	39	-48	35	36	37	33	-59	-8	48	69	-31	189	8	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											189
121	-49	78	-5	-6	-7	-59	38	-9	49	70	-32	189	-86	128	25	26	27	28	-75	29	19	30	60	-22	189	
-24	54	8	37	-1	7	63	-33	237	-197	71	-33	189	37	38	-5	-6	-7	-8	95	-9	-15	31	61	-23	189	
27	3	26	20	25	-20	0	30	-10	50	72	-34	189	-110	130	8	77	-11	7	10	20	-19	39	62	-24	189	
28	2	3	5	1	42	-1	31	-11	51	-467	505	189	32	-12	16	20	25	20	33	-3	-20	40	63	-25	189	
29	1	14	-11	26	22	-2	32	-12	52	73	-35	189	33	-13	13	5	31	32	9	21	165	-145	-386	424	189	
-151	135	93	-10	-11	-12	33	34	-13	53	74	-36	189	34	-14	44	-21	36	22	8	22	-21	41	64	-26	189	
43	-74	-63	40	41	42	44	38	-14	54	75	-37	189	35	-15	12	-28	65	11	15	36	-22	42	65	-27	189	
-767	-657	3639	-16	-17	-18	-19	-1985	20	-29	76	-38	189	36	-16	18	58	-35	19	36	15	-23	43	66	-28	189	
807	697	-3599	56	57	58	59	2025	-29	20	77	-39	189	89	-26	-26	200	-27	-28	-29	-30	43	-15	67	-29	189	
-3815	61	62	63	3489	64	65	66	67	68	19	-20	189	51	-49	46	-180	47	48	49	50	44	45	68	-30	189	
3853	-23	-24	-25	-3451	-26	-27	-28	-29	-30	-20	19	189	965	807	53	54	-3941	55	56	57	2025	59	19	-20	189	
189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	-927	-769	-15	-16	3979	-17	-18	-19	-1987	-21	-20	19	189	
189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	

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9	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											190													
-40	62	-33	-34	-35	-36	332	-37	-38	-39	120	-32	190	9	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											190
61	60	53	54	55	56	-312	57	58	59	52	-63	190	9	55	-1	7	0	30	38	-18	-20	50	66	-26	190	
-43	63	29	30	-21	26	27	28	63	-32	45	-25	190	26	20	25	-1	-1	31	39	-19	-21	51	67	-27	190	
-44	64	76	-22	51	4	3	2	-32	68	46	-26	190	3	6	19	42	63	-33	40	-20	-22	52	68	-28	190	
-45	65	3	27	9	85	-11	7	36	-6	47	-27	190	32	-11	27	22	-2	32	-140	160	-23	53	69	-29	190	
-46	66	18	12	16	20	25	29	9	21	48	-28	190	30	2	27	1	15	25	41	-21	281	-251	-430	470	190	
402	-382	19	11	13	6	39	32	8	22	-256	276	190	0	28	3	29	25	15	42	-22	-24	54	70	-30	190	
-47	67	20	10	52	-21	37	22	7	23	49	-29	190	34	144	35	-226	36	37	10	50	-25	55	71	-31	190	
-48	68	-49	90	66	-1	-2	-3	24	25	50	-30	190	-14	-124	-15	246	-16	-17	50	10	-26	56	72	-32	190	
-49	69	34	-8	-36	31	32	33	35	29	51	-31	190	-456	-14	-15	-877	-1995	3514	-18	-19	15	15	73	-33	190	
-47	-116	907	38	39	40	-3052	41	42	2025	44	229	190	486	44	45	907	2025	-3484	48	49	15	15	74	-34	190	
136	104	-887	-18	-19	-20	3072	-21	-22	-2005	-106	-24	190	58	928	59	60	-1220	61	62	63	64	65	20	-30	190	
190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	-18	-888	-19	-20	1260	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-30	20	190	
190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	

9	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											190													
38	39	-48	35	36	37	32	-59	-8	48	69	-29	190	9	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											190
121	-49	78	-5	-6	-7	-59	37	-9	49	70	-30	190	9	-86	127	25	26	27	28	-75	29	19	30	60	-20	190
-24	54	9	35	-1	7	63	-33	237	-197	71	-31	190	37	38	-5	-6	-7	-8	95	-9	-16	31	61	-21	190	
27	3	26	20	25	-21	0	30	-10	50	72	-32	190	-110	130	9	75	-11	7	10	20	-19	39	62	-22	190	
28	2	3	6	-1	42	-1	31	-11	51	-457	497	190	32	-12	16	20	25	19	33	-3	-20	40	63	-23	190	
29	1	12	-11	27	22	-2	32	-12	52	73	-33	190	33	-13	13	6	29	32	9	21	165	-145	-376	416	190	
-152	135	93	-10	-11	-12	33	34	-13	53	74	-34	190	34	-14	42	-21	37	22	8	22	-21	41	64	-24	190	
43	-75	-63	40	41	42	44	38	-14	54	75	-35	190	35	-15	12	-30	67	11	15	35	-22	42	65	-25	190	
-867	-759	3841	-16	-17	-18	-19	-1985	20	-30	76	-36	190	36	-16	18	60	-37	19	35	15	-23	43	66	-26	190	
907	799	-3801	56	57	58	59	2025	-30	20	77	-37	190	88	-25	-26	200	-27	-28	-29	-30	43	-16	67	-27	190	
-4014	61	62	63	3698	64	65	66	67	68	20	-30	190	51	-50	46	-180	47	48	49	50	44	45	68	-28	190	
4054	-21	-22	-23	-3658	-24	-25	-26	-27	-28	-30	20	190	1066	907	53	54	-4132	55	56	57	2025	59	20	-30	190	
190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	-1026	-867	-13	-14	4172	-15	-16	-17	-1985	-19	-30	20	190	
190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	

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10	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										191
-40	62	-33	-34	-35	-36	332	-37	-38	-39	121	-32	191
61	60	53	54	55	56	-312	57	58	59	52	-62	191
-43	63	29	30	-21	26	27	28	64	-32	45	-25	191
-44	64	76	-22	51	4	3	2	-32	69	46	-26	191
-45	65	3	27	10	85	-11	7	36	-6	47	-27	191
-46	66	18	12	16	20	25	30	9	21	48	-28	191
402	-382	19	11	13	7	39	32	8	22	-256	276	191
-47	67	20	10	52	-21	38	22	7	23	49	-29	191
-48	68	-48	90	66	-1	-2	-3	24	25	50	-30	191
-49	69	34	-7	-36	31	32	33	35	29	51	-31	191
-46	-116	1007	38	39	40	-3152	41	42	2025	44	229	191
136	105	-987	-18	-19	-20	3172	-21	-22	-2005	-106	-24	191
191	191	191	191	191	191	191	191	191	191	191	191	191

10	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										191
10	55	-1	7	0	30	38	-18	-20	50	66	-26	191
26	20	25	0	-1	31	39	-19	-21	51	67	-27	191
3	7	19	42	63	-33	40	-20	-22	52	68	-28	191
32	-11	28	22	-2	32	-140	160	-23	53	69	-29	191
30	2	27	1	15	26	41	-21	281	-251	-430	470	191
0	28	3	29	26	15	42	-22	-24	54	70	-30	191
34	145	35	-227	36	37	10	51	-25	55	71	-31	191
-14	-125	-15	247	-16	-17	51	10	-26	56	72	-32	191
-456	-14	-15	-977	-1995	3614	-18	-19	15	16	73	-33	191
486	44	45	1007	2025	-3584	48	49	16	15	74	-34	191
58	1029	59	60	-1321	61	62	63	64	65	20	-29	191
-18	-989	-19	-20	1361	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-29	20	191
191	191	191	191	191	191	191	191	191	191	191	191	191

10	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										191
38	39	-48	35	36	37	33	-59	-8	48	69	-29	191
121	-49	78	-5	-6	-7	-59	38	-9	49	70	-30	191
-24	54	10	35	-1	7	63	-33	237	-197	71	-31	191
27	3	26	20	25	-20	0	30	-10	50	72	-32	191
28	2	3	7	-1	42	-1	31	-11	51	-457	497	191
29	1	12	-11	28	22	-2	32	-12	52	73	-33	191
-151	135	93	-10	-11	-12	33	34	-13	53	74	-34	191
43	-74	-63	40	41	42	44	38	-14	54	75	-35	191
-967	-859	4041	-16	-17	-18	-19	-1985	20	-29	76	-36	191
1007	899	-4001	56	57	58	59	2025	-29	20	77	-37	191
-4215	61	62	63	3899	64	65	66	67	68	20	-29	191
4255	-21	-22	-23	-3859	-24	-25	-26	-27	-28	-29	20	191
191	191	191	191	191	191	191	191	191	191	191	191	191

10	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										191
-86	128	25	26	27	28	-75	29	19	30	60	-20	191
37	38	-5	-6	-7	-8	95	-9	-15	31	61	-21	191
-110	130	10	75	-11	7	10	20	-19	39	62	-22	191
32	-12	16	20	25	20	33	-3	-20	40	63	-23	191
33	-13	13	7	29	32	9	21	165	-145	-376	416	191
34	-14	42	-21	38	22	8	22	-21	41	64	-24	191
35	-15	12	-30	67	11	15	36	-22	42	65	-25	191
36	-16	18	60	-37	19	36	15	-23	43	66	-26	191
89	-26	-26	200	-27	-28	-29	-30	43	-15	67	-27	191
51	-49	46	-180	47	48	49	50	44	45	68	-28	191
1165	1007	53	54	-4331	55	56	57	2025	59	20	-29	191
-1125	-967	-13	-14	4371	-15	-16	-17	-1985	-19	-29	20	191
191	191	191	191	191	191	191	191	191	191	191	191	191

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11	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										192	11	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										192
-39	62	-32	-33	-34	-35	329	-36	-37	-38	116	-31	192	11	53	-1	7	0	30	38	-18	-20	50	66	-24	192
61	60	53	54	55	56	-308	57	58	59	52	-65	192	26	20	25	-1	-1	31	39	-19	-21	51	67	-25	192
-42	63	29	30	-21	26	27	28	63	-32	45	-24	192	3	8	17	42	63	-33	40	-20	-22	52	68	-26	192
-43	64	76	-22	51	4	3	2	-32	68	46	-25	192	30	-11	29	22	-2	32	-140	160	-23	53	69	-27	192
-44	65	3	27	11	83	-11	7	36	-6	47	-26	192	32	2	25	1	15	25	41	-21	281	-251	-420	462	192
-45	66	18	12	16	20	25	29	9	21	48	-27	192	-2	28	5	29	25	15	42	-22	-24	54	70	-28	192
399	-378	19	11	13	8	37	32	8	22	-252	273	192	34	142	35	-224	36	37	10	50	-25	55	71	-29	192
-46	67	20	10	50	-21	39	22	7	23	49	-28	192	-14	-122	-15	244	-16	-17	50	10	-26	56	72	-30	192
-47	68	-49	90	66	-1	-2	-3	24	25	50	-29	192	-454	-14	-15	-1077	-1995	3712	-18	-19	15	15	73	-31	192
-48	69	34	-8	-36	31	32	33	35	29	51	-30	192	484	44	45	1107	2025	-3682	48	49	15	15	74	-32	192
-49	-114	1107	38	39	40	-3248	41	42	2025	44	227	192	58	1126	59	60	-1408	61	62	63	64	65	21	-39	192
135	100	-1086	-17	-18	-19	3269	-20	-21	-2004	-104	-23	192	-16	-1084	-17	-18	1450	-19	-20	-21	-22	-23	-39	21	192
192	192	192	192	192	192	192	192	192	192	192	192	192	192	192	192	192	192	192	192	192	192	192	192	192	192

11	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										192	11	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										192
38	39	-48	35	36	37	32	-59	-8	48	69	-27	192	-86	127	25	26	27	28	-75	29	19	30	60	-18	192
121	-49	78	-5	-6	-7	-59	37	-9	49	70	-28	192	37	38	-5	-6	-7	-8	95	-9	-16	31	61	-19	192
-24	54	11	33	-1	7	63	-33	237	-197	71	-29	192	-110	130	11	73	-11	7	10	20	-19	39	62	-20	192
27	3	26	20	25	-21	0	30	-10	50	72	-30	192	32	-12	16	20	25	19	33	-3	-20	40	63	-21	192
28	2	3	8	-3	42	-1	31	-11	51	-447	489	192	33	-13	13	8	27	32	9	21	165	-145	-366	408	192
29	1	10	-11	29	22	-2	32	-12	52	73	-31	192	34	-14	40	-21	39	22	8	22	-21	41	64	-22	192
-152	135	93	-10	-11	-12	33	34	-13	53	74	-32	192	35	-15	12	-32	69	11	15	35	-22	42	65	-23	192
43	-75	-63	40	41	42	44	38	-14	54	75	-33	192	36	-16	18	62	-39	19	35	15	-23	43	66	-24	192
-1067	-961	4243	-16	-17	-18	-19	-1985	20	-30	76	-34	192	88	-25	-26	200	-27	-28	-29	-30	43	-16	67	-25	192
1107	1001	-4203	56	57	58	59	2025	-30	20	77	-35	192	51	-50	46	-180	47	48	49	50	44	45	68	-26	192
-4414	61	62	63	4108	64	65	66	67	68	21	-39	192	1266	1107	53	54	-4522	55	56	57	2025	59	21	-39	192
4456	-19	-20	-21	-4066	-22	-23	-24	-25	-26	-39	21	192	-1224	-1065	-11	-12	4564	-13	-14	-15	-1983	-17	-39	21	192
192	192	192	192	192	192	192	192	192	192	192	192	192	192	192	192	192	192	192	192	192	192	192	192	192	192

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12	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										193	12	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										193
-39	62	-32	-33	-34	-35	329	-36	-37	-38	117	-31	193	12	53	-1	7	0	30	38	-18	-20	50	66	-24	193
61	60	53	54	55	56	-308	57	58	59	52	-64	193	26	20	25	0	-1	31	39	-19	-21	51	67	-25	193
-42	63	29	30	-21	26	27	28	64	-32	45	-24	193	3	9	17	42	63	-33	40	-20	-22	52	68	-26	193
-43	64	76	-22	51	4	3	2	-32	69	46	-25	193	30	-11	30	22	-2	32	-140	160	-23	53	69	-27	193
-44	65	3	27	12	83	-11	7	36	-6	47	-26	193	32	2	25	1	15	26	41	-21	281	-251	-420	462	193
-45	66	18	12	16	20	25	30	9	21	48	-27	193	-2	28	5	29	26	15	42	-22	-24	54	70	-28	193
399	-378	19	11	13	9	37	32	8	22	-252	273	193	34	143	35	-225	36	37	10	51	-25	55	71	-29	193
-46	67	20	10	50	-21	40	22	7	23	49	-28	193	-14	-123	-15	245	-16	-17	51	10	-26	56	72	-30	193
-47	68	-48	90	66	-1	-2	-3	24	25	50	-29	193	-454	-14	-15	-1177	-1995	3812	-18	-19	15	16	73	-31	193
-48	69	34	-7	-36	31	32	33	35	29	51	-30	193	484	44	45	1207	2025	-3782	48	49	16	15	74	-32	193
-48	-114	1207	38	39	40	-3348	41	42	2025	44	227	193	58	1227	59	60	-1509	61	62	63	64	65	21	-38	193
135	101	-1186	-17	-18	-19	3369	-20	-21	-2004	-104	-23	193	-16	-1185	-17	-18	1551	-19	-20	-21	-22	-23	-38	21	193
193	193	193	193	193	193	193	193	193	193	193	193	193	193	193	193	193	193	193	193	193	193	193	193	193	193

12	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										193	12	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										193
38	39	-48	35	36	37	33	-59	-8	48	69	-27	193	-86	128	25	26	27	28	-75	29	19	30	60	-18	193
121	-49	78	-5	-6	-7	-59	38	-9	49	70	-28	193	37	38	-5	-6	-7	-8	95	-9	-15	31	61	-19	193
-24	54	12	33	-1	7	63	-33	237	-197	71	-29	193	-110	130	12	73	-11	7	10	20	-19	39	62	-20	193
27	3	26	20	25	-20	0	30	-10	50	72	-30	193	32	-12	16	20	25	20	33	-3	-20	40	63	-21	193
28	2	3	9	-3	42	-1	31	-11	51	-447	489	193	33	-13	13	9	27	32	9	21	165	-145	-366	408	193
29	1	10	-11	30	22	-2	32	-12	52	73	-31	193	34	-14	40	-21	40	22	8	22	-21	41	64	-22	193
-151	135	93	-10	-11	-12	33	34	-13	53	74	-32	193	35	-15	12	-32	69	11	15	36	-22	42	65	-23	193
43	-74	-63	40	41	42	44	38	-14	54	75	-33	193	36	-16	18	62	-39	19	36	15	-23	43	66	-24	193
-1167	-1061	4443	-16	-17	-18	-19	-1985	20	-29	76	-34	193	89	-26	-26	200	-27	-28	-29	-30	43	-15	67	-25	193
1207	1101	-4403	56	57	58	59	2025	-29	20	77	-35	193	51	-49	46	-180	47	48	49	50	44	45	68	-26	193
-4615	61	62	63	4309	64	65	66	67	68	21	-38	193	1365	1207	53	54	-4721	55	56	57	2025	59	21	-38	193
4657	-19	-20	-21	-4267	-22	-23	-24	-25	-26	-38	21	193	-1323	-1165	-11	-12	4763	-13	-14	-15	-1983	-17	-38	21	193
193	193	193	193	193	193	193	193	193	193	193	193	193	193	193	193	193	193	193	193	193	193	193	193	193	193

■ 194th Day of the Year - 13.07.2025

13	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											194
	-38	62	-31	-32	-33	-34	326	-35	-36	-37	112	-30	194
	61	60	53	54	55	56	-304	57	58	59	52	-67	194
	-41	63	29	30	-21	26	27	28	63	-32	45	-23	194
	-42	64	76	-22	51	4	3	2	-32	68	46	-24	194
	-43	65	3	27	13	81	-11	7	36	-6	47	-25	194
	-44	66	18	12	16	20	25	29	9	21	48	-26	194
	396	-374	19	11	13	10	35	32	8	22	-248	270	194
	-45	67	20	10	48	-21	41	22	7	23	49	-27	194
	-46	68	-49	90	66	-1	-2	-3	24	25	50	-28	194
	-47	69	34	-8	-36	31	32	33	35	29	51	-29	194
	-51	-112	1307	38	39	40	-3444	41	42	2025	44	225	194
	134	96	-1285	-16	-17	-18	3466	-19	-20	-2003	-102	-22	194
194	194	194	194	194	194	194	194	194	194	194	194	194	194

13	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											194
	13	51	-1	7	0	30	38	-18	-20	50	66	-22	194
	26	20	25	-1	-1	31	39	-19	-21	51	67	-23	194
	3	10	15	42	63	-33	40	-20	-22	52	68	-24	194
	28	-11	31	22	-2	32	-140	160	-23	53	69	-25	194
	34	2	23	1	15	25	41	-21	281	-251	-410	454	194
	-4	28	7	29	25	15	42	-22	-24	54	70	-26	194
	34	140	35	-222	36	37	10	50	-25	55	71	-27	194
	-14	-120	-15	242	-16	-17	50	10	-26	56	72	-28	194
	-452	-14	-15	-1277	-1995	3910	-18	-19	15	15	73	-29	194
	482	44	45	1307	2025	-3880	48	49	15	15	74	-30	194
	58	1324	59	60	-1596	61	62	63	64	65	22	-48	194
	-14	-1280	-15	-16	1640	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	-48	22	194
194	194	194	194	194	194	194	194	194	194	194	194	194	194

13	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											194
	38	39	-48	35	36	37	32	-59	-8	48	69	-25	194
	121	-49	78	-5	-6	-7	-59	37	-9	49	70	-26	194
	-24	54	13	31	-1	7	63	-33	237	-197	71	-27	194
	27	3	26	20	25	-21	0	30	-10	50	72	-28	194
	28	2	3	10	-5	42	-1	31	-11	51	-437	481	194
	29	1	8	-11	31	22	-2	32	-12	52	73	-29	194
	-152	135	93	-10	-11	-12	33	34	-13	53	74	-30	194
	43	-75	-63	40	41	42	44	38	-14	54	75	-31	194
	-1267	-1163	4645	-16	-17	-18	-19	-1985	20	-30	76	-32	194
	1307	1203	-4605	56	57	58	59	2025	-30	20	77	-33	194
	-4814	61	62	63	4518	64	65	66	67	68	22	-48	194
	4858	-17	-18	-19	-4474	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-48	22	194
194	194	194	194	194	194	194	194	194	194	194	194	194	194

13	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											194
	-86	127	25	26	27	28	-75	29	19	30	60	-16	194
	37	38	-5	-6	-7	-8	95	-9	-16	31	61	-17	194
	-110	130	13	71	-11	7	10	20	-19	39	62	-18	194
	32	-12	16	20	25	19	33	-3	-20	40	63	-19	194
	33	-13	13	10	25	32	9	21	165	-145	-356	400	194
	34	-14	38	-21	41	22	8	22	-21	41	64	-20	194
	35	-15	12	-34	71	11	15	35	-22	42	65	-21	194
	36	-16	18	64	-41	19	35	15	-23	43	66	-22	194
	88	-25	-26	200	-27	-28	-29	-30	43	-16	67	-23	194
	51	-50	46	-180	47	48	49	50	44	45	68	-24	194
	1466	1307	53	54	-4912	55	56	57	2025	59	22	-48	194
	-1422	-1263	-9	-10	4956	-11	-12	-13	-1981	-15	-48	22	194
194	194	194	194	194	194	194	194	194	194	194	194	194	194

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14	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										195	14	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										195		
	-38	62	-31	-32	-33	-34	326	-35	-36	-37	113	-30	195		14	51	-1	7	0	30	38	-18	-20	50	66	-22	195
	61	60	53	54	55	56	-304	57	58	59	52	-66	195		26	20	25	0	-1	31	39	-19	-21	51	67	-23	195
	-41	63	29	30	-21	26	27	28	64	-32	45	-23	195		3	11	15	42	63	-33	40	-20	-22	52	68	-24	195
	-42	64	76	-22	51	4	3	2	-32	69	46	-24	195		28	-11	32	22	-2	32	-140	160	-23	53	69	-25	195
	-43	65	3	27	14	81	-11	7	36	-6	47	-25	195		34	2	23	1	15	26	41	-21	281	-251	-410	454	195
	-44	66	18	12	16	20	25	30	9	21	48	-26	195		-4	28	7	29	26	15	42	-22	-24	54	70	-26	195
	396	-374	19	11	13	11	35	32	8	22	-248	270	195		34	141	35	-223	36	37	10	51	-25	55	71	-27	195
	-45	67	20	10	48	-21	42	22	7	23	49	-27	195		-14	-121	-15	243	-16	-17	51	10	-26	56	72	-28	195
	-46	68	-48	90	66	-1	-2	-3	24	25	50	-28	195		-452	-14	-15	-1377	-1995	4010	-18	-19	15	16	73	-29	195
	-47	69	34	-7	-36	31	32	33	35	29	51	-29	195		482	44	45	1407	2025	-3980	48	49	16	15	74	-30	195
	-50	-112	1407	38	39	40	-3544	41	42	2025	44	225	195		58	1425	59	60	-1697	61	62	63	64	65	22	-47	195
	134	97	-1385	-16	-17	-18	3566	-19	-20	-2003	-102	-22	195		-14	-1381	-15	-16	1741	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	-47	22	195
	195	195	195	195	195	195	195	195	195	195	195	195	195		195	195	195	195	195	195	195	195	195	195	195	195	195

14	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										195	14	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										195		
	38	39	-48	35	36	37	33	-59	-8	48	69	-25	195		-86	128	25	26	27	28	-75	29	19	30	60	-16	195
	121	-49	78	-5	-6	-7	-59	38	-9	49	70	-26	195		37	38	-5	-6	-7	-8	95	-9	-15	31	61	-17	195
	-24	54	14	31	-1	7	63	-33	237	-197	71	-27	195		-110	130	14	71	-11	7	10	20	-19	39	62	-18	195
	27	3	26	20	25	-20	0	30	-10	50	72	-28	195		32	-12	16	20	25	20	33	-3	-20	40	63	-19	195
	28	2	3	11	-5	42	-1	31	-11	51	-437	481	195		33	-13	13	11	25	32	9	21	165	-145	-356	400	195
	29	1	8	-11	32	22	-2	32	-12	52	73	-29	195		34	-14	38	-21	42	22	8	22	-21	41	64	-20	195
	-151	135	93	-10	-11	-12	33	34	-13	53	74	-30	195		35	-15	12	-34	71	11	15	36	-22	42	65	-21	195
	43	-74	-63	40	41	42	44	38	-14	54	75	-31	195		36	-16	18	64	-41	19	36	15	-23	43	66	-22	195
	-1367	-1263	4845	-16	-17	-18	-19	-1985	20	-29	76	-32	195		89	-26	-26	200	-27	-28	-29	-30	43	-15	67	-23	195
	1407	1303	-4805	56	57	58	59	2025	-29	20	77	-33	195		51	-49	46	-180	47	48	49	50	44	45	68	-24	195
	-5015	61	62	63	4719	64	65	66	67	68	22	-47	195		1565	1407	53	54	-5111	55	56	57	2025	59	22	-47	195
	5059	-17	-18	-19	-4675	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-47	22	195		-1521	-1363	-9	-10	5155	-11	-12	-13	-1981	-15	-47	22	195
	195	195	195	195	195	195	195	195	195	195	195	195	195		195	195	195	195	195	195	195	195	195	195	195	195	195

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15	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										196	15	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										196			
	-37	62	-30	-31	-32	-33	323	-34	-35	-36	108	-29	196		15	49	-1	7	0	30	38	-18	-20	50	66	-20	196	
	61	60	53	54	55	56	-300	57	58	59	52	-69	196		26	20	25	-1	-1	31	39	-19	-21	51	67	-21	196	
	-40	63	29	30	-21	26	27	28	63	-32	45	-22	196		3	12	13	42	63	-33	40	-20	-22	52	68	-22	196	
	-41	64	76	-22	51	4	3	2	-32	68	46	-23	196		26	-11	33	22	-2	32	-140	160	-23	53	69	-23	196	
	-42	65	3	27	15	79	-11	7	36	-6	47	-24	196		36	2	21	1	15	25	41	-21	281	-251	-400	446	196	
	-43	66	18	12	16	20	25	29	9	21	48	-25	196		-6	28	9	29	25	15	42	-22	-24	54	70	-24	196	
	393	-370	19	11	13	12	33	32	8	22	-244	267	196		34	138	35	-220	36	37	10	50	-25	55	71	-25	196	
	-44	67	20	10	46	-21	43	22	7	23	49	-26	196		-14	-118	-15	240	-16	-17	50	10	-26	56	72	-26	196	
	-45	68	-49	90	66	-1	-2	-3	24	25	50	-27	196		-450	-14	-15	-1477	-1995	4108	-18	-19	15	15	73	-27	196	
	-46	69	34	-8	-36	31	32	33	35	29	51	-28	196		480	44	45	1507	2025	-4078	48	49	15	15	74	-28	196	
	-53	-110	1507	38	39	40	-3640	41	42	2025	44	223	196		58	1522	59	60	-1784	61	62	63	64	65	23	-57	196	
	133	92	-1484	-15	-16	-17	3663	-18	-19	-2002	-100	-21	196		-12	-1476	-13	-14	1830	-15	-16	-17	-18	-19	-57	23	196	
196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196

15	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										196	15	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										196			
	38	39	-48	35	36	37	32	-59	-8	48	69	-23	196		-86	127	25	26	27	28	-75	29	19	30	60	-14	196	
	121	-49	78	-5	-6	-7	-59	37	-9	49	70	-24	196		37	38	-5	-6	-7	-8	95	-9	-16	31	61	-15	196	
	-24	54	15	29	-1	7	63	-33	237	-197	71	-25	196		-110	130	15	69	-11	7	10	20	-19	39	62	-16	196	
	27	3	26	20	25	-21	0	30	-10	50	72	-26	196		32	-12	16	20	25	19	33	-3	-20	40	63	-17	196	
	28	2	3	12	-7	42	-1	31	-11	51	-427	473	196		33	-13	13	12	23	32	9	21	165	-145	-346	392	196	
	29	1	6	-11	33	22	-2	32	-12	52	73	-27	196		34	-14	36	-21	43	22	8	22	-21	41	64	-18	196	
	-152	135	93	-10	-11	-12	33	34	-13	53	74	-28	196		35	-15	12	-36	73	11	15	35	-22	42	65	-19	196	
	43	-75	-63	40	41	42	44	38	-14	54	75	-29	196		36	-16	18	66	-43	19	35	15	-23	43	66	-20	196	
	-1467	-1365	5047	-16	-17	-18	-19	-1985	20	-30	76	-30	196		88	-25	-26	200	-27	-28	-29	-30	43	-16	67	-21	196	
	1507	1405	-5007	56	57	58	59	2025	-30	20	77	-31	196		51	-50	46	-180	47	48	49	50	44	45	68	-22	196	
	-5214	61	62	63	4928	64	65	66	67	68	23	-57	196		1666	1507	53	54	-5302	55	56	57	2025	59	23	-57	196	
	5260	-15	-16	-17	-4882	-18	-19	-20	-21	-22	-57	23	196		-1620	-1461	-7	-8	5348	-9	-10	-11	-1979	-13	-57	23	196	
196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196

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16	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/										©IJT	197												
-37	62	-30	-31	-32	-33	323	-34	-35	-36	109	-29	197	16	49	-1	7	0	30	38	-18	-20	50	66	-20	197
61	60	53	54	55	56	-300	57	58	59	52	-68	197	26	20	25	0	-1	31	39	-19	-21	51	67	-21	197
-40	63	29	30	-21	26	27	28	64	-32	45	-22	197	3	13	13	42	63	-33	40	-20	-22	52	68	-22	197
-41	64	76	-22	51	4	3	2	-32	69	46	-23	197	26	-11	34	22	-2	32	-140	160	-23	53	69	-23	197
-42	65	3	27	16	79	-11	7	36	-6	47	-24	197	36	2	21	1	15	26	41	-21	281	-251	-400	446	197
-43	66	18	12	16	20	25	30	9	21	48	-25	197	-6	28	9	29	26	15	42	-22	-24	54	70	-24	197
393	-370	19	11	13	13	33	32	8	22	-244	267	197	34	139	35	-221	36	37	10	51	-25	55	71	-25	197
-44	67	20	10	46	-21	44	22	7	23	49	-26	197	-14	-119	-15	241	-16	-17	51	10	-26	56	72	-26	197
-45	68	-48	90	66	-1	-2	-3	24	25	50	-27	197	-450	-14	-15	-1577	-1995	4208	-18	-19	15	16	73	-27	197
-46	69	34	-7	-36	31	32	33	35	29	51	-28	197	480	44	45	1607	2025	-4178	48	49	16	15	74	-28	197
-52	-110	1607	38	39	40	-3740	41	42	2025	44	223	197	58	1623	59	60	-1885	61	62	63	64	65	23	-56	197
133	93	-1584	-15	-16	-17	3763	-18	-19	-2002	-100	-21	197	-12	-1577	-13	-14	1931	-15	-16	-17	-18	-19	-56	23	197
197	197	197	197	197	197	197	197	197	197	197	197	197	197	197	197	197	197	197	197	197	197	197	197	197	197

16	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/										©IJT	197												
38	39	-48	35	36	37	33	-59	-8	48	69	-23	197	-86	128	25	26	27	28	-75	29	19	30	60	-14	197
121	-49	78	-5	-6	-7	-59	38	-9	49	70	-24	197	37	38	-5	-6	-7	-8	95	-9	-15	31	61	-15	197
-24	54	16	29	-1	7	63	-33	237	-197	71	-25	197	-110	130	16	69	-11	7	10	20	-19	39	62	-16	197
27	3	26	20	25	-20	0	30	-10	50	72	-26	197	32	-12	16	20	25	20	33	-3	-20	40	63	-17	197
28	2	3	13	-7	42	-1	31	-11	51	-427	473	197	33	-13	13	13	23	32	9	21	165	-145	-346	392	197
29	1	6	-11	34	22	-2	32	-12	52	73	-27	197	34	-14	36	-21	44	22	8	22	-21	41	64	-18	197
-151	135	93	-10	-11	-12	33	34	-13	53	74	-28	197	35	-15	12	-36	73	11	15	36	-22	42	65	-19	197
43	-74	-63	40	41	42	44	38	-14	54	75	-29	197	36	-16	18	66	-43	19	36	15	-23	43	66	-20	197
-1567	-1465	5247	-16	-17	-18	-19	-1985	20	-29	76	-30	197	89	-26	-26	200	-27	-28	-29	-30	43	-15	67	-21	197
1607	1505	-5207	56	57	58	59	2025	-29	20	77	-31	197	51	-49	46	-180	47	48	49	50	44	45	68	-22	197
-5415	61	62	63	5129	64	65	66	67	68	23	-56	197	1765	1607	53	54	-5501	55	56	57	2025	59	23	-56	197
5461	-15	-16	-17	-5083	-18	-19	-20	-21	-22	-56	23	197	-1719	-1561	-7	-8	5547	-9	-10	-11	-1979	-13	-56	23	197
197	197	197	197	197	197	197	197	197	197	197	197	197	197	197	197	197	197	197	197	197	197	197	197	197	197

■ 198th Day of the Year - 17.07.2025

17	mgc	12x12	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										198
-36	62	-29	-30	-31	-32	320	-33	-34	-35	104	-28	198	
61	60	53	54	55	56	-296	57	58	59	52	-71	198	
-39	63	29	30	-21	26	27	28	63	-32	45	-21	198	
-40	64	76	-22	51	4	3	2	-32	68	46	-22	198	
-41	65	3	27	17	77	-11	7	36	-6	47	-23	198	
-42	66	18	12	16	20	25	29	9	21	48	-24	198	
390	-366	19	11	13	14	31	32	8	22	-240	264	198	
-43	67	20	10	44	-21	45	22	7	23	49	-25	198	
-44	68	-49	90	66	-1	-2	-3	24	25	50	-26	198	
-45	69	34	-8	-36	31	32	33	35	29	51	-27	198	
-55	-108	1707	38	39	40	-3836	41	42	2025	44	221	198	
132	88	-1683	-14	-15	-16	3860	-17	-18	-2001	-98	-20	198	
198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	

17	mgc	12x12	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										198
17	47	-1	7	0	30	38	-18	-20	50	66	-18	198	
26	20	25	-1	-1	31	39	-19	-21	51	67	-19	198	
3	14	11	42	63	-33	40	-20	-22	52	68	-20	198	
24	-11	35	22	-2	32	-140	160	-23	53	69	-21	198	
38	2	19	1	15	25	41	-21	281	-251	-390	438	198	
-8	28	11	29	25	15	42	-22	-24	54	70	-22	198	
34	136	35	-218	36	37	10	50	-25	55	71	-23	198	
-14	-116	-15	238	-16	-17	50	10	-26	56	72	-24	198	
-448	-14	-15	-1677	-1995	4306	-18	-19	15	15	73	-25	198	
478	44	45	1707	2025	-4276	48	49	15	15	74	-26	198	
58	1720	59	60	-1972	61	62	63	64	65	24	-66	198	
-10	-1672	-11	-12	2020	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	-66	24	198	
198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	

17	mgc	12x12	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										198
38	39	-48	35	36	37	32	-59	-8	48	69	-21	198	
121	-49	78	-5	-6	-7	-59	37	-9	49	70	-22	198	
-24	54	17	27	-1	7	63	-33	237	-197	71	-23	198	
27	3	26	20	25	-21	0	30	-10	50	72	-24	198	
28	2	3	14	-9	42	-1	31	-11	51	-417	465	198	
29	1	4	-11	35	22	-2	32	-12	52	73	-25	198	
-152	135	93	-10	-11	-12	33	34	-13	53	74	-26	198	
43	-75	-63	40	41	42	44	38	-14	54	75	-27	198	
-1667	-1567	5449	-16	-17	-18	-19	-1985	20	-30	76	-28	198	
1707	1607	-5409	56	57	58	59	2025	-30	20	77	-29	198	
-5614	61	62	63	5338	64	65	66	67	68	24	-66	198	
5662	-13	-14	-15	-5290	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	-66	24	198	
198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	

17	mgc	12x12	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										198
-86	127	25	26	27	28	-75	29	19	30	60	-12	198	
37	38	-5	-6	-7	-8	95	-9	-16	31	61	-13	198	
-110	130	17	67	-11	7	10	20	-19	39	62	-14	198	
32	-12	16	20	25	19	33	-3	-20	40	63	-15	198	
33	-13	13	14	21	32	9	21	165	-145	-336	384	198	
34	-14	34	-21	45	22	8	22	-21	41	64	-16	198	
35	-15	12	-38	75	11	15	35	-22	42	65	-17	198	
36	-16	18	68	-45	19	35	15	-23	43	66	-18	198	
88	-25	-26	200	-27	-28	-29	-30	43	-16	67	-19	198	
51	-50	46	-180	47	48	49	50	44	45	68	-20	198	
1866	1707	53	54	-5692	55	56	57	2025	59	24	-66	198	
-1818	-1659	-5	-6	5740	-7	-8	-9	-1977	-11	-66	24	198	
198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	

■ 199th Day of the Year - 18.07.2025

18	mgc	12x12	Inder J. Taneja	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	199	18	mgc	12x12	Inder J. Taneja	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	199												
-36	62	-29	-30	-31	-32	320	-33	-34	-35	105	-28	199	18	47	-1	7	0	30	38	-18	-20	50	66	-18	199
61	60	53	54	55	56	-296	57	58	59	52	-70	199	26	20	25	0	-1	31	39	-19	-21	51	67	-19	199
-39	63	29	30	-21	26	27	28	64	-32	45	-21	199	3	15	11	42	63	-33	40	-20	-22	52	68	-20	199
-40	64	76	-22	51	4	3	2	-32	69	46	-22	199	24	-11	36	22	-2	32	-140	160	-23	53	69	-21	199
-41	65	3	27	18	77	-11	7	36	-6	47	-23	199	38	2	19	1	15	26	41	-21	281	-251	-390	438	199
-42	66	18	12	16	20	25	30	9	21	48	-24	199	-8	28	11	29	26	15	42	-22	-24	54	70	-22	199
390	-366	19	11	13	15	31	32	8	22	-240	264	199	34	137	35	-219	36	37	10	51	-25	55	71	-23	199
-43	67	20	10	44	-21	46	22	7	23	49	-25	199	-14	-117	-15	239	-16	-17	51	10	-26	56	72	-24	199
-44	68	-48	90	66	-1	-2	-3	24	25	50	-26	199	-448	-14	-15	-1777	-1995	4406	-18	-19	15	16	73	-25	199
-45	69	34	-7	-36	31	32	33	35	29	51	-27	199	478	44	45	1807	2025	-4376	48	49	16	15	74	-26	199
-54	-108	1807	38	39	40	-3936	41	42	2025	44	221	199	58	1821	59	60	-2073	61	62	63	64	65	24	-65	199
132	89	-1783	-14	-15	-16	3960	-17	-18	-2001	-98	-20	199	-10	-1773	-11	-12	2121	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	-65	24	199
199	199	199	199	199	199	199	199	199	199	199	199	199	199	199	199	199	199	199	199	199	199	199	199	199	

18	mgc	12x12	Inder J. Taneja	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	199	18	mgc	12x12	Inder J. Taneja	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	199												
38	39	-48	35	36	37	33	-59	-8	48	69	-21	199	-86	128	25	26	27	28	-75	29	19	30	60	-12	199
121	-49	78	-5	-6	-7	-59	38	-9	49	70	-22	199	37	38	-5	-6	-7	-8	95	-9	-15	31	61	-13	199
-24	54	18	27	-1	7	63	-33	237	-197	71	-23	199	-110	130	18	67	-11	7	10	20	-19	39	62	-14	199
27	3	26	20	25	-20	0	30	-10	50	72	-24	199	32	-12	16	20	25	20	33	-3	-20	40	63	-15	199
28	2	3	15	-9	42	-1	31	-11	51	-417	465	199	33	-13	13	15	21	32	9	21	165	-145	-336	384	199
29	1	4	-11	36	22	-2	32	-12	52	73	-25	199	34	-14	34	-21	46	22	8	22	-21	41	64	-16	199
-151	135	93	-10	-11	-12	33	34	-13	53	74	-26	199	35	-15	12	-38	75	11	15	36	-22	42	65	-17	199
43	-74	-63	40	41	42	44	38	-14	54	75	-27	199	36	-16	18	68	-45	19	36	15	-23	43	66	-18	199
-1767	-1667	5649	-16	-17	-18	-19	-1985	20	-29	76	-28	199	89	-26	-26	200	-27	-28	-29	-30	43	-15	67	-19	199
1807	1707	-5609	56	57	58	59	2025	-29	20	77	-29	199	51	-49	46	-180	47	48	49	50	44	45	68	-20	199
-5815	61	62	63	5539	64	65	66	67	68	24	-65	199	1965	1807	53	54	-5891	55	56	57	2025	59	24	-65	199
5863	-13	-14	-15	-5491	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	-65	24	199	-1917	-1759	-5	-6	5939	-7	-8	-9	-1977	-11	-65	24	199
199	199	199	199	199	199	199	199	199	199	199	199	199	199	199	199	199	199	199	199	199	199	199	199	199	

■ 200th Day of the Year - 19.07.2025

19	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										200	19	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										200	
	-35	62	-28	-29	-30	-31	317	-32	-33	-34	100	-27	200	19	45	-1	7	0	30	38	-18	-20	50	66	-16	200
	61	60	53	54	55	56	-292	57	58	59	52	-73	200	26	20	25	-1	-1	31	39	-19	-21	51	67	-17	200
	-38	63	29	30	-21	26	27	28	63	-32	45	-20	200	3	16	9	42	63	-33	40	-20	-22	52	68	-18	200
	-39	64	76	-22	51	4	3	2	-32	68	46	-21	200	22	-11	37	22	-2	32	-140	160	-23	53	69	-19	200
	-40	65	3	27	19	75	-11	7	36	-6	47	-22	200	40	2	17	1	15	25	41	-21	281	-251	-380	430	200
	-41	66	18	12	16	20	25	29	9	21	48	-23	200	-10	28	13	29	25	15	42	-22	-24	54	70	-20	200
	387	-362	19	11	13	16	29	32	8	22	-236	261	200	34	134	35	-216	36	37	10	50	-25	55	71	-21	200
	-42	67	20	10	42	-21	47	22	7	23	49	-24	200	-14	-114	-15	236	-16	-17	50	10	-26	56	72	-22	200
	-43	68	-49	90	66	-1	-2	-3	24	25	50	-25	200	-446	-14	-15	-1877	-1995	4504	-18	-19	15	15	73	-23	200
	-44	69	34	-8	-36	31	32	33	35	29	51	-26	200	476	44	45	1907	2025	-4474	48	49	15	15	74	-24	200
	-57	-106	1907	38	39	40	-4032	41	42	2025	44	219	200	58	1918	59	60	-2160	61	62	63	64	65	25	-75	200
	131	84	-1882	-13	-14	-15	4057	-16	-17	-2000	-96	-19	200	-8	-1868	-9	-10	2210	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	-75	25	200
	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200

19	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										200	19	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										200	
	38	39	-48	35	36	37	32	-59	-8	48	69	-19	200	-86	127	25	26	27	28	-75	29	19	30	60	-10	200
	121	-49	78	-5	-6	-7	-59	37	-9	49	70	-20	200	37	38	-5	-6	-7	-8	95	-9	-16	31	61	-11	200
	-24	54	19	25	-1	7	63	-33	237	-197	71	-21	200	-110	130	19	65	-11	7	10	20	-19	39	62	-12	200
	27	3	26	20	25	-21	0	30	-10	50	72	-22	200	32	-12	16	20	25	19	33	-3	-20	40	63	-13	200
	28	2	3	16	-11	42	-1	31	-11	51	-407	457	200	33	-13	13	16	19	32	9	21	165	-145	-326	376	200
	29	1	2	-11	37	22	-2	32	-12	52	73	-23	200	34	-14	32	-21	47	22	8	22	-21	41	64	-14	200
	-152	135	93	-10	-11	-12	33	34	-13	53	74	-24	200	35	-15	12	-40	77	11	15	35	-22	42	65	-15	200
	43	-75	-63	40	41	42	44	38	-14	54	75	-25	200	36	-16	18	70	-47	19	35	15	-23	43	66	-16	200
	-1867	-1769	5851	-16	-17	-18	-19	-1985	20	-30	76	-26	200	88	-25	-26	200	-27	-28	-29	-30	43	-16	67	-17	200
	1907	1809	-5811	56	57	58	59	2025	-30	20	77	-27	200	51	-50	46	-180	47	48	49	50	44	45	68	-18	200
	-6014	61	62	63	5748	64	65	66	67	68	25	-75	200	2066	1907	53	54	-6082	55	56	57	2025	59	25	-75	200
	6064	-11	-12	-13	-5698	-14	-15	-16	-17	-18	-75	25	200	-2016	-1857	-3	-4	6132	-5	-6	-7	-1975	-9	-75	25	200
	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200

■ 201st Day of the Year - 20.07.2025

20	mgc	12x12	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										201
-35	62	-28	-29	-30	-31	317	-32	-33	-34	101	-27	201	
61	60	53	54	55	56	-292	57	58	59	52	-72	201	
-38	63	29	30	-21	26	27	28	64	-32	45	-20	201	
-39	64	76	-22	51	4	3	2	-32	69	46	-21	201	
-40	65	3	27	20	75	-11	7	36	-6	47	-22	201	
-41	66	18	12	16	20	25	30	9	21	48	-23	201	
387	-362	19	11	13	17	29	32	8	22	-236	261	201	
-42	67	20	10	42	-21	48	22	7	23	49	-24	201	
-43	68	-48	90	66	-1	-2	-3	24	25	50	-25	201	
-44	69	34	-7	-36	31	32	33	35	29	51	-26	201	
-56	-106	2007	38	39	40	-4132	41	42	2025	44	219	201	
131	85	-1982	-13	-14	-15	4157	-16	-17	-2000	-96	-19	201	
201	201	201	201	201	201	201	201	201	201	201	201	201	

20	mgc	12x12	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										201
20	45	-1	7	0	30	38	-18	-20	50	66	-16	201	
26	20	25	0	-1	31	39	-19	-21	51	67	-17	201	
3	17	9	42	63	-33	40	-20	-22	52	68	-18	201	
22	-11	38	22	-2	32	-140	160	-23	53	69	-19	201	
40	2	17	1	15	26	41	-21	281	-251	-380	430	201	
-10	28	13	29	26	15	42	-22	-24	54	70	-20	201	
34	135	35	-217	36	37	10	51	-25	55	71	-21	201	
-14	-115	-15	237	-16	-17	51	10	-26	56	72	-22	201	
-446	-14	-15	-1977	-1995	4604	-18	-19	15	16	73	-23	201	
476	44	45	2007	2025	-4574	48	49	16	15	74	-24	201	
58	2019	59	60	-2261	61	62	63	64	65	25	-74	201	
-8	-1969	-9	-10	2311	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	-74	25	201	
201	201	201	201	201	201	201	201	201	201	201	201	201	

20	mgc	12x12	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										201
38	39	-48	35	36	37	33	-59	-8	48	69	-19	201	
121	-49	78	-5	-6	-7	-59	38	-9	49	70	-20	201	
-24	54	20	25	-1	7	63	-33	237	-197	71	-21	201	
27	3	26	20	25	-20	0	30	-10	50	72	-22	201	
28	2	3	17	-11	42	-1	31	-11	51	-407	457	201	
29	1	2	-11	38	22	-2	32	-12	52	73	-23	201	
-151	135	93	-10	-11	-12	33	34	-13	53	74	-24	201	
43	-74	-63	40	41	42	44	38	-14	54	75	-25	201	
-1967	-1869	6051	-16	-17	-18	-19	-1985	20	-29	76	-26	201	
2007	1909	-6011	56	57	58	59	2025	-29	20	77	-27	201	
-6215	61	62	63	5949	64	65	66	67	68	25	-74	201	
6265	-11	-12	-13	-5899	-14	-15	-16	-17	-18	-74	25	201	
201	201	201	201	201	201	201	201	201	201	201	201	201	

20	mgc	12x12	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										201
-86	128	25	26	27	28	-75	29	19	30	60	-10	201	
37	38	-5	-6	-7	-8	95	-9	-15	31	61	-11	201	
-110	130	20	65	-11	7	10	20	-19	39	62	-12	201	
32	-12	16	20	25	20	33	-3	-20	40	63	-13	201	
33	-13	13	17	19	32	9	21	165	-145	-326	376	201	
34	-14	32	-21	48	22	8	22	-21	41	64	-14	201	
35	-15	12	-40	77	11	15	36	-22	42	65	-15	201	
36	-16	18	70	-47	19	36	15	-23	43	66	-16	201	
89	-26	-26	200	-27	-28	-29	-30	43	-15	67	-17	201	
51	-49	46	-180	47	48	49	50	44	45	68	-18	201	
2165	2007	53	54	-6281	55	56	57	2025	59	25	-74	201	
-2115	-1957	-3	-4	6331	-5	-6	-7	-1975	-9	-74	25	201	
201	201	201	201	201	201	201	201	201	201	201	201	201	

■ 202nd Day of the Year - 21.07.2025

21	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										202	21	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										202
-34	62	-27	-28	-29	-30	314	-31	-32	-33	96	-26	202	21	43	-1	7	0	30	38	-18	-20	50	66	-14	202
61	60	53	54	55	56	-288	57	58	59	52	-75	202	26	20	25	-1	-1	31	39	-19	-21	51	67	-15	202
-37	63	29	30	-21	26	27	28	63	-32	45	-19	202	3	18	7	42	63	-33	40	-20	-22	52	68	-16	202
-38	64	76	-22	51	4	3	2	-32	68	46	-20	202	20	-11	39	22	-2	32	-140	160	-23	53	69	-17	202
-39	65	3	27	21	73	-11	7	36	-6	47	-21	202	42	2	15	1	15	25	41	-21	281	-251	-370	422	202
-40	66	18	12	16	20	25	29	9	21	48	-22	202	-12	28	15	29	25	15	42	-22	-24	54	70	-18	202
384	-358	19	11	13	18	27	32	8	22	-232	258	202	34	132	35	-214	36	37	10	50	-25	55	71	-19	202
-41	67	20	10	40	-21	49	22	7	23	49	-23	202	-14	-112	-15	234	-16	-17	50	10	-26	56	72	-20	202
-42	68	-49	90	66	-1	-2	-3	24	25	50	-24	202	-444	-14	-15	-2077	-1995	4702	-18	-19	15	15	73	-21	202
-43	69	34	-8	-36	31	32	33	35	29	51	-25	202	474	44	45	2107	2025	-4672	48	49	15	15	74	-22	202
-59	-104	2107	38	39	40	-4228	41	42	2025	44	217	202	58	2116	59	60	-2348	61	62	63	64	65	26	-84	202
130	80	-2081	-12	-13	-14	4254	-15	-16	-1999	-94	-18	202	-6	-2064	-7	-8	2400	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	-84	26	202
202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202

21	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										202	21	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										202
38	39	-48	35	36	37	32	-59	-8	48	69	-17	202	-86	127	25	26	27	28	-75	29	19	30	60	-8	202
121	-49	78	-5	-6	-7	-59	37	-9	49	70	-18	202	37	38	-5	-6	-7	-8	95	-9	-16	31	61	-9	202
-24	54	21	23	-1	7	63	-33	237	-197	71	-19	202	-110	130	21	63	-11	7	10	20	-19	39	62	-10	202
27	3	26	20	25	-21	0	30	-10	50	72	-20	202	32	-12	16	20	25	19	33	-3	-20	40	63	-11	202
28	2	3	18	-13	42	-1	31	-11	51	-397	449	202	33	-13	13	18	17	32	9	21	165	-145	-316	368	202
29	1	0	-11	39	22	-2	32	-12	52	73	-21	202	34	-14	30	-21	49	22	8	22	-21	41	64	-12	202
-152	135	93	-10	-11	-12	33	34	-13	53	74	-22	202	35	-15	12	-42	79	11	15	35	-22	42	65	-13	202
43	-75	-63	40	41	42	44	38	-14	54	75	-23	202	36	-16	18	72	-49	19	35	15	-23	43	66	-14	202
-2067	-1971	6253	-16	-17	-18	-19	-1985	20	-30	76	-24	202	88	-25	-26	200	-27	-28	-29	-30	43	-16	67	-15	202
2107	2011	-6213	56	57	58	59	2025	-30	20	77	-25	202	51	-50	46	-180	47	48	49	50	44	45	68	-16	202
-6414	61	62	63	6158	64	65	66	67	68	26	-84	202	2266	2107	53	54	-6472	55	56	57	2025	59	26	-84	202
6466	-9	-10	-11	-6106	-12	-13	-14	-15	-16	-84	26	202	-2214	-2055	-1	-2	6524	-3	-4	-5	-1973	-7	-84	26	202
202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202

■ 203rd Day of the Year - 22.07.2025

22	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											203
-34	62	-27	-28	-29	-30	314	-31	-32	-33	97	-26	203	
61	60	53	54	55	56	-288	57	58	59	52	-74	203	
-37	63	29	30	-21	26	27	28	64	-32	45	-19	203	
-38	64	76	-22	51	4	3	2	-32	69	46	-20	203	
-39	65	3	27	22	73	-11	7	36	-6	47	-21	203	
-40	66	18	12	16	20	25	30	9	21	48	-22	203	
384	-358	19	11	13	19	27	32	8	22	-232	258	203	
-41	67	20	10	40	-21	50	22	7	23	49	-23	203	
-42	68	-48	90	66	-1	-2	-3	24	25	50	-24	203	
-43	69	34	-7	-36	31	32	33	35	29	51	-25	203	
-58	-104	2207	38	39	40	-4328	41	42	2025	44	217	203	
130	81	-2181	-12	-13	-14	4354	-15	-16	-1999	-94	-18	203	
203	203	203	203	203	203	203	203	203	203	203	203	203	

22	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											203
22	43	-1	7	0	30	38	-18	-20	50	66	-14	203	
26	20	25	0	-1	31	39	-19	-21	51	67	-15	203	
3	19	7	42	63	-33	40	-20	-22	52	68	-16	203	
20	-11	40	22	-2	32	-140	160	-23	53	69	-17	203	
42	2	15	1	15	26	41	-21	281	-251	-370	422	203	
-12	28	15	29	26	15	42	-22	-24	54	70	-18	203	
34	133	35	-215	36	37	10	51	-25	55	71	-19	203	
-14	-113	-15	235	-16	-17	51	10	-26	56	72	-20	203	
-444	-14	-15	-2177	-1995	4802	-18	-19	15	16	73	-21	203	
474	44	45	2207	2025	-4772	48	49	16	15	74	-22	203	
58	2217	59	60	-2449	61	62	63	64	65	26	-83	203	
-6	-2165	-7	-8	2501	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	-83	26	203	
203	203	203	203	203	203	203	203	203	203	203	203	203	

22	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											203
38	39	-48	35	36	37	33	-59	-8	48	69	-17	203	
121	-49	78	-5	-6	-7	-59	38	-9	49	70	-18	203	
-24	54	22	23	-1	7	63	-33	237	-197	71	-19	203	
27	3	26	20	25	-20	0	30	-10	50	72	-20	203	
28	2	3	19	-13	42	-1	31	-11	51	-397	449	203	
29	1	0	-11	40	22	-2	32	-12	52	73	-21	203	
-151	135	93	-10	-11	-12	33	34	-13	53	74	-22	203	
43	-74	-63	40	41	42	44	38	-14	54	75	-23	203	
-2167	-2071	6453	-16	-17	-18	-19	-1985	20	-29	76	-24	203	
2207	2111	-6413	56	57	58	59	2025	-29	20	77	-25	203	
-6615	61	62	63	6359	64	65	66	67	68	26	-83	203	
6667	-9	-10	-11	-6307	-12	-13	-14	-15	-16	-83	26	203	
203	203	203	203	203	203	203	203	203	203	203	203	203	

22	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											203
-86	128	25	26	27	28	-75	29	19	30	60	-8	203	
37	38	-5	-6	-7	-8	95	-9	-15	31	61	-9	203	
-110	130	22	63	-11	7	10	20	-19	39	62	-10	203	
32	-12	16	20	25	20	33	-3	-20	40	63	-11	203	
33	-13	13	19	17	32	9	21	165	-145	-316	368	203	
34	-14	30	-21	50	22	8	22	-21	41	64	-12	203	
35	-15	12	-42	79	11	15	36	-22	42	65	-13	203	
36	-16	18	72	-49	19	36	15	-23	43	66	-14	203	
89	-26	-26	200	-27	-28	-29	-30	43	-15	67	-15	203	
51	-49	46	-180	47	48	49	50	44	45	68	-16	203	
2365	2207	53	54	-6671	55	56	57	2025	59	26	-83	203	
-2313	-2155	-1	-2	6723	-3	-4	-5	-1973	-7	-83	26	203	
203	203	203	203	203	203	203	203	203	203	203	203	203	

■ 204th Day of the Year - 23.07.2025

23	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										204
-33	62	-26	-27	-28	-29	311	-30	-31	-32	92	-25	204
61	60	53	54	55	56	-284	57	58	59	52	-77	204
-36	63	29	30	-21	26	27	28	63	-32	45	-18	204
-37	64	76	-22	51	4	3	2	-32	68	46	-19	204
-38	65	3	27	23	71	-11	7	36	-6	47	-20	204
-39	66	18	12	16	20	25	29	9	21	48	-21	204
381	-354	19	11	13	20	25	32	8	22	-228	255	204
-40	67	20	10	38	-21	51	22	7	23	49	-22	204
-41	68	-49	90	66	-1	-2	-3	24	25	50	-23	204
-42	69	34	-8	-36	31	32	33	35	29	51	-24	204
-61	-102	2307	38	39	40	-4424	41	42	2025	44	215	204
129	76	-2280	-11	-12	-13	4451	-14	-15	-1998	-92	-17	204
204	204	204	204	204	204	204	204	204	204	204	204	204

23	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										204
23	41	-1	7	0	30	38	-18	-20	50	66	-12	204
26	20	25	-1	-1	31	39	-19	-21	51	67	-13	204
3	20	5	42	63	-33	40	-20	-22	52	68	-14	204
18	-11	41	22	-2	32	-140	160	-23	53	69	-15	204
44	2	13	1	15	25	41	-21	281	-251	-360	414	204
-14	28	17	29	25	15	42	-22	-24	54	70	-16	204
34	130	35	-212	36	37	10	50	-25	55	71	-17	204
-14	-110	-15	232	-16	-17	50	10	-26	56	72	-18	204
-442	-14	-15	-2277	-1995	4900	-18	-19	15	15	73	-19	204
472	44	45	2307	2025	-4870	48	49	15	15	74	-20	204
58	2314	59	60	-2536	61	62	63	64	65	27	-93	204
-4	-2260	-5	-6	2590	-7	-8	-9	-10	-11	-93	27	204
204	204	204	204	204	204	204	204	204	204	204	204	204

23	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										204
38	39	-48	35	36	37	32	-59	-8	48	69	-15	204
121	-49	78	-5	-6	-7	-59	37	-9	49	70	-16	204
-24	54	23	21	-1	7	63	-33	237	-197	71	-17	204
27	3	26	20	25	-21	0	30	-10	50	72	-18	204
28	2	3	20	-15	42	-1	31	-11	51	-387	441	204
29	1	-2	-11	41	22	-2	32	-12	52	73	-19	204
-152	135	93	-10	-11	-12	33	34	-13	53	74	-20	204
43	-75	-63	40	41	42	44	38	-14	54	75	-21	204
-2267	-2173	6655	-16	-17	-18	-19	-1985	20	-30	76	-22	204
2307	2213	-6615	56	57	58	59	2025	-30	20	77	-23	204
-6814	61	62	63	6568	64	65	66	67	68	27	-93	204
6868	-7	-8	-9	-6514	-10	-11	-12	-13	-14	-93	27	204
204	204	204	204	204	204	204	204	204	204	204	204	204

23	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										204
-86	127	25	26	27	28	-75	29	19	30	60	-6	204
37	38	-5	-6	-7	-8	95	-9	-16	31	61	-7	204
-110	130	23	61	-11	7	10	20	-19	39	62	-8	204
32	-12	16	20	25	19	33	-3	-20	40	63	-9	204
33	-13	13	20	15	32	9	21	165	-145	-306	360	204
34	-14	28	-21	51	22	8	22	-21	41	64	-10	204
35	-15	12	-44	81	11	15	35	-22	42	65	-11	204
36	-16	18	74	-51	19	35	15	-23	43	66	-12	204
88	-25	-26	200	-27	-28	-29	-30	43	-16	67	-13	204
51	-50	46	-180	47	48	49	50	44	45	68	-14	204
2466	2307	53	54	-6862	55	56	57	2025	59	27	-93	204
-2412	-2253	1	0	6916	-1	-2	-3	-1971	-5	-93	27	204
204	204	204	204	204	204	204	204	204	204	204	204	204

■ 205th Day of the Year - 24.07.2025

24	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										205	24	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										205			
	-33	62	-26	-27	-28	-29	311	-30	-31	-32	93	-25	205		24	41	-1	7	0	30	38	-18	-20	50	66	-12	205	
	61	60	53	54	55	56	-284	57	58	59	52	-76	205		26	20	25	0	-1	31	39	-19	-21	51	67	-13	205	
	-36	63	29	30	-21	26	27	28	64	-32	45	-18	205		3	21	5	42	63	-33	40	-20	-22	52	68	-14	205	
	-37	64	76	-22	51	4	3	2	-32	69	46	-19	205		18	-11	42	22	-2	32	-140	160	-23	53	69	-15	205	
	-38	65	3	27	24	71	-11	7	36	-6	47	-20	205		44	2	13	1	15	26	41	-21	281	-251	-360	414	205	
	-39	66	18	12	16	20	25	30	9	21	48	-21	205		-14	28	17	29	26	15	42	-22	-24	54	70	-16	205	
	381	-354	19	11	13	21	25	32	8	22	-228	255	205		34	131	35	-213	36	37	10	51	-25	55	71	-17	205	
	-40	67	20	10	38	-21	52	22	7	23	49	-22	205		-14	-111	-15	233	-16	-17	51	10	-26	56	72	-18	205	
	-41	68	-48	90	66	-1	-2	-3	24	25	50	-23	205		-442	-14	-15	-2377	-1995	5000	-18	-19	15	16	73	-19	205	
	-42	69	34	-7	-36	31	32	33	35	29	51	-24	205		472	44	45	2407	2025	-4970	48	49	16	15	74	-20	205	
	-60	-102	2407	38	39	40	-4524	41	42	2025	44	215	205		58	2415	59	60	-2637	61	62	63	64	65	27	-92	205	
	129	77	-2380	-11	-12	-13	4551	-14	-15	-1998	-92	-17	205		-4	-2361	-5	-6	2691	-7	-8	-9	-10	-11	-92	27	205	
205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205

24	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										205	24	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										205			
	38	39	-48	35	36	37	33	-59	-8	48	69	-15	205		-86	128	25	26	27	28	-75	29	19	30	60	-6	205	
	121	-49	78	-5	-6	-7	-59	38	-9	49	70	-16	205		37	38	-5	-6	-7	-8	95	-9	-15	31	61	-7	205	
	-24	54	24	21	-1	7	63	-33	237	-197	71	-17	205		-110	130	24	61	-11	7	10	20	-19	39	62	-8	205	
	27	3	26	20	25	-20	0	30	-10	50	72	-18	205		32	-12	16	20	25	20	33	-3	-20	40	63	-9	205	
	28	2	3	21	-15	42	-1	31	-11	51	-387	441	205		33	-13	13	21	15	32	9	21	165	-145	-306	360	205	
	29	1	-2	-11	42	22	-2	32	-12	52	73	-19	205		34	-14	28	-21	52	22	8	22	-21	41	64	-10	205	
	-151	135	93	-10	-11	-12	33	34	-13	53	74	-20	205		35	-15	12	-44	81	11	15	36	-22	42	65	-11	205	
	43	-74	-63	40	41	42	44	38	-14	54	75	-21	205		36	-16	18	74	-51	19	36	15	-23	43	66	-12	205	
	-2367	-2273	6855	-16	-17	-18	-19	-1985	20	-29	76	-22	205		89	-26	-26	200	-27	-28	-29	-30	43	-15	67	-13	205	
	2407	2313	-6815	56	57	58	59	2025	-29	20	77	-23	205		51	-49	46	-180	47	48	49	50	44	45	68	-14	205	
	-7015	61	62	63	6769	64	65	66	67	68	27	-92	205		2565	2407	53	54	-7061	55	56	57	2025	59	27	-92	205	
	7069	-7	-8	-9	-6715	-10	-11	-12	-13	-14	-92	27	205		-2511	-2353	1	0	7115	-1	-2	-3	-1971	-5	-92	27	205	
205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205

■ 206th Day of the Year - 25.07.2025

25	mgc	12x12	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										206
-32	62	-25	-26	-27	-28	308	-29	-30	-31	88	-24	206	
61	60	53	54	55	56	-280	57	58	59	52	-79	206	
-35	63	29	30	-21	26	27	28	63	-32	45	-17	206	
-36	64	76	-22	51	4	3	2	-32	68	46	-18	206	
-37	65	3	27	25	69	-11	7	36	-6	47	-19	206	
-38	66	18	12	16	20	25	29	9	21	48	-20	206	
378	-350	19	11	13	22	23	32	8	22	-224	252	206	
-39	67	20	10	36	-21	53	22	7	23	49	-21	206	
-40	68	-49	90	66	-1	-2	-3	24	25	50	-22	206	
-41	69	34	-8	-36	31	32	33	35	29	51	-23	206	
-63	-100	2507	38	39	40	-4620	41	42	2025	44	213	206	
128	72	-2479	-10	-11	-12	4648	-13	-14	-1997	-90	-16	206	
206	206	206	206	206	206	206	206	206	206	206	206	206	

25	mgc	12x12	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										206
25	39	-1	7	0	30	38	-18	-20	50	66	-10	206	
26	20	25	-1	-1	31	39	-19	-21	51	67	-11	206	
3	22	3	42	63	-33	40	-20	-22	52	68	-12	206	
16	-11	43	22	-2	32	-140	160	-23	53	69	-13	206	
46	2	11	1	15	25	41	-21	281	-251	-350	406	206	
-16	28	19	29	25	15	42	-22	-24	54	70	-14	206	
34	128	35	-210	36	37	10	50	-25	55	71	-15	206	
-14	-108	-15	230	-16	-17	50	10	-26	56	72	-16	206	
-440	-14	-15	-2477	-1995	5098	-18	-19	15	15	73	-17	206	
470	44	45	2507	2025	-5068	48	49	15	15	74	-18	206	
58	2512	59	60	-2724	61	62	63	64	65	28	-102	206	
-2	-2456	-3	-4	2780	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	-102	28	206	
206	206	206	206	206	206	206	206	206	206	206	206	206	

25	mgc	12x12	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										206
38	39	-48	35	36	37	32	-59	-8	48	69	-13	206	
121	-49	78	-5	-6	-7	-59	37	-9	49	70	-14	206	
-24	54	25	19	-1	7	63	-33	237	-197	71	-15	206	
27	3	26	20	25	-21	0	30	-10	50	72	-16	206	
28	2	3	22	-17	42	-1	31	-11	51	-377	433	206	
29	1	-4	-11	43	22	-2	32	-12	52	73	-17	206	
-152	135	93	-10	-11	-12	33	34	-13	53	74	-18	206	
43	-75	-63	40	41	42	44	38	-14	54	75	-19	206	
-2467	-2375	7057	-16	-17	-18	-19	-1985	20	-30	76	-20	206	
2507	2415	-7017	56	57	58	59	2025	-30	20	77	-21	206	
-7214	61	62	63	6978	64	65	66	67	68	28	-102	206	
7270	-5	-6	-7	-6922	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-102	28	206	
206	206	206	206	206	206	206	206	206	206	206	206	206	

25	mgc	12x12	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										206
-86	127	25	26	27	28	-75	29	19	30	60	-4	206	
37	38	-5	-6	-7	-8	95	-9	-16	31	61	-5	206	
-110	130	25	59	-11	7	10	20	-19	39	62	-6	206	
32	-12	16	20	25	19	33	-3	-20	40	63	-7	206	
33	-13	13	22	13	32	9	21	165	-145	-296	352	206	
34	-14	26	-21	53	22	8	22	-21	41	64	-8	206	
35	-15	12	-46	83	11	15	35	-22	42	65	-9	206	
36	-16	18	76	-53	19	35	15	-23	43	66	-10	206	
88	-25	-26	200	-27	-28	-29	-30	43	-16	67	-11	206	
51	-50	46	-180	47	48	49	50	44	45	68	-12	206	
2666	2507	53	54	-7252	55	56	57	2025	59	28	-102	206	
-2610	-2451	3	2	7308	1	0	-1	-1969	-3	-102	28	206	
206	206	206	206	206	206	206	206	206	206	206	206	206	

■ 207th Day of the Year - 26.07.2025

26	mgc	12x12	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										207
-32	62	-25	-26	-27	-28	308	-29	-30	-31	89	-24	207	
61	60	53	54	55	56	-280	57	58	59	52	-78	207	
-35	63	29	30	-21	26	27	28	64	-32	45	-17	207	
-36	64	76	-22	51	4	3	2	-32	69	46	-18	207	
-37	65	3	27	26	69	-11	7	36	-6	47	-19	207	
-38	66	18	12	16	20	25	30	9	21	48	-20	207	
378	-350	19	11	13	23	23	32	8	22	-224	252	207	
-39	67	20	10	36	-21	54	22	7	23	49	-21	207	
-40	68	-48	90	66	-1	-2	-3	24	25	50	-22	207	
-41	69	34	-7	-36	31	32	33	35	29	51	-23	207	
-62	-100	2607	38	39	40	-4720	41	42	2025	44	213	207	
128	73	-2579	-10	-11	-12	4748	-13	-14	-1997	-90	-16	207	
207	207	207	207	207	207	207	207	207	207	207	207	207	

26	mgc	12x12	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										207
26	39	-1	7	0	30	38	-18	-20	50	66	-10	207	
26	20	25	0	-1	31	39	-19	-21	51	67	-11	207	
3	23	3	42	63	-33	40	-20	-22	52	68	-12	207	
16	-11	44	22	-2	32	-140	160	-23	53	69	-13	207	
46	2	11	1	15	26	41	-21	281	-251	-350	406	207	
-16	28	19	29	26	15	42	-22	-24	54	70	-14	207	
34	129	35	-211	36	37	10	51	-25	55	71	-15	207	
-14	-109	-15	231	-16	-17	51	10	-26	56	72	-16	207	
-440	-14	-15	-2577	-1995	5198	-18	-19	15	16	73	-17	207	
470	44	45	2607	2025	-5168	48	49	16	15	74	-18	207	
58	2613	59	60	-2825	61	62	63	64	65	28	-101	207	
-2	-2557	-3	-4	2881	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	-101	28	207	
207	207	207	207	207	207	207	207	207	207	207	207	207	

26	mgc	12x12	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										207
38	39	-48	35	36	37	33	-59	-8	48	69	-13	207	
121	-49	78	-5	-6	-7	-59	38	-9	49	70	-14	207	
-24	54	26	19	-1	7	63	-33	237	-197	71	-15	207	
27	3	26	20	25	-20	0	30	-10	50	72	-16	207	
28	2	3	23	-17	42	-1	31	-11	51	-377	433	207	
29	1	-4	-11	44	22	-2	32	-12	52	73	-17	207	
-151	135	93	-10	-11	-12	33	34	-13	53	74	-18	207	
43	-74	-63	40	41	42	44	38	-14	54	75	-19	207	
-2567	-2475	7257	-16	-17	-18	-19	-1985	20	-29	76	-20	207	
2607	2515	-7217	56	57	58	59	2025	-29	20	77	-21	207	
-7415	61	62	63	7179	64	65	66	67	68	28	-101	207	
7471	-5	-6	-7	-7123	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-101	28	207	
207	207	207	207	207	207	207	207	207	207	207	207	207	

26	mgc	12x12	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										207
-86	128	25	26	27	28	-75	29	19	30	60	-4	207	
37	38	-5	-6	-7	-8	95	-9	-15	31	61	-5	207	
-110	130	26	59	-11	7	10	20	-19	39	62	-6	207	
32	-12	16	20	25	20	33	-3	-20	40	63	-7	207	
33	-13	13	23	13	32	9	21	165	-145	-296	352	207	
34	-14	26	-21	54	22	8	22	-21	41	64	-8	207	
35	-15	12	-46	83	11	15	36	-22	42	65	-9	207	
36	-16	18	76	-53	19	36	15	-23	43	66	-10	207	
89	-26	-26	200	-27	-28	-29	-30	43	-15	67	-11	207	
51	-49	46	-180	47	48	49	50	44	45	68	-12	207	
2765	2607	53	54	-7451	55	56	57	2025	59	28	-101	207	
-2709	-2551	3	2	7507	1	0	-1	-1969	-3	-101	28	207	
207	207	207	207	207	207	207	207	207	207	207	207	207	

■ 208th Day of the Year - 27.07.2025

27	mgc												208	27	mgc												208
-31	62	-24	-25	-26	-27	305	-28	-29	-30	84	-23	208	27	37	-1	7	0	30	38	-18	-20	50	66	-8	208		
61	60	53	54	55	56	-276	57	58	59	52	-81	208	26	20	25	-1	-1	31	39	-19	-21	51	67	-9	208		
-34	63	29	30	-21	26	27	28	63	-32	45	-16	208	3	24	1	42	63	-33	40	-20	-22	52	68	-10	208		
-35	64	76	-22	51	4	3	2	-32	68	46	-17	208	14	-11	45	22	-2	32	-140	160	-23	53	69	-11	208		
-36	65	3	27	27	67	-11	7	36	-6	47	-18	208	48	2	9	1	15	25	41	-21	281	-251	-340	398	208		
-37	66	18	12	16	20	25	29	9	21	48	-19	208	-18	28	21	29	25	15	42	-22	-24	54	70	-12	208		
375	-346	19	11	13	24	21	32	8	22	-220	249	208	34	126	35	-208	36	37	10	50	-25	55	71	-13	208		
-38	67	20	10	34	-21	55	22	7	23	49	-20	208	-14	-106	-15	228	-16	-17	50	10	-26	56	72	-14	208		
-39	68	-49	90	66	-1	-2	-3	24	25	50	-21	208	-438	-14	-15	-2677	-1995	5296	-18	-19	15	15	73	-15	208		
-40	69	34	-8	-36	31	32	33	35	29	51	-22	208	468	44	45	2707	2025	-5266	48	49	15	15	74	-16	208		
-65	-98	2707	38	39	40	-4816	41	42	2025	44	211	208	58	2710	59	60	-2912	61	62	63	64	65	29	-111	208		
127	68	-2678	-9	-10	-11	4845	-12	-13	-1996	-88	-15	208	0	-2652	-1	-2	2970	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-111	29	208		
208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208		

27	mgc												208	27	mgc												208
38	39	-48	35	36	37	32	-59	-8	48	69	-11	208	-86	127	25	26	27	28	-75	29	19	30	60	-2	208		
121	-49	78	-5	-6	-7	-59	37	-9	49	70	-12	208	37	38	-5	-6	-7	-8	95	-9	-16	31	61	-3	208		
-24	54	27	17	-1	7	63	-33	237	-197	71	-13	208	-110	130	27	57	-11	7	10	20	-19	39	62	-4	208		
27	3	26	20	25	-21	0	30	-10	50	72	-14	208	32	-12	16	20	25	19	33	-3	-20	40	63	-5	208		
28	2	3	24	-19	42	-1	31	-11	51	-367	425	208	33	-13	13	24	11	32	9	21	165	-145	-286	344	208		
29	1	-6	-11	45	22	-2	32	-12	52	73	-15	208	34	-14	24	-21	55	22	8	22	-21	41	64	-6	208		
-152	135	93	-10	-11	-12	33	34	-13	53	74	-16	208	35	-15	12	-48	85	11	15	35	-22	42	65	-7	208		
43	-75	-63	40	41	42	44	38	-14	54	75	-17	208	36	-16	18	78	-55	19	35	15	-23	43	66	-8	208		
-2667	-2577	7459	-16	-17	-18	-19	-1985	20	-30	76	-18	208	88	-25	-26	200	-27	-28	-29	-30	43	-16	67	-9	208		
2707	2617	-7419	56	57	58	59	2025	-30	20	77	-19	208	51	-50	46	-180	47	48	49	50	44	45	68	-10	208		
-7614	61	62	63	7388	64	65	66	67	68	29	-111	208	2866	2707	53	54	-7642	55	56	57	2025	59	29	-111	208		
7672	-3	-4	-5	-7330	-6	-7	-8	-9	-10	-111	29	208	-2808	-2649	5	4	7700	3	2	1	-1967	-1	-111	29	208		
208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208		

■ 209th Day of the Year - 28.07.2025

28	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										209
-31	62	-24	-25	-26	-27	305	-28	-29	-30	85	-23	209
61	60	53	54	55	56	-276	57	58	59	52	-80	209
-34	63	29	30	-21	26	27	28	64	-32	45	-16	209
-35	64	76	-22	51	4	3	2	-32	69	46	-17	209
-36	65	3	27	28	67	-11	7	36	-6	47	-18	209
-37	66	18	12	16	20	25	30	9	21	48	-19	209
375	-346	19	11	13	25	21	32	8	22	-220	249	209
-38	67	20	10	34	-21	56	22	7	23	49	-20	209
-39	68	-48	90	66	-1	-2	-3	24	25	50	-21	209
-40	69	34	-7	-36	31	32	33	35	29	51	-22	209
-64	-98	2807	38	39	40	-4916	41	42	2025	44	211	209
127	69	-2778	-9	-10	-11	4945	-12	-13	-1996	-88	-15	209
209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209

28	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										209
28	37	-1	7	0	30	38	-18	-20	50	66	-8	209
26	20	25	0	-1	31	39	-19	-21	51	67	-9	209
3	25	1	42	63	-33	40	-20	-22	52	68	-10	209
14	-11	46	22	-2	32	-140	160	-23	53	69	-11	209
48	2	9	1	15	26	41	-21	281	-251	-340	398	209
-18	28	21	29	26	15	42	-22	-24	54	70	-12	209
34	127	35	-209	36	37	10	51	-25	55	71	-13	209
-14	-107	-15	229	-16	-17	51	10	-26	56	72	-14	209
-438	-14	-15	-2777	-1995	5396	-18	-19	15	16	73	-15	209
468	44	45	2807	2025	-5366	48	49	16	15	74	-16	209
58	2811	59	60	-3013	61	62	63	64	65	29	-110	209
0	-2753	-1	-2	3071	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-110	29	209
209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209

28	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										209
38	39	-48	35	36	37	33	-59	-8	48	69	-11	209
121	-49	78	-5	-6	-7	-59	38	-9	49	70	-12	209
-24	54	28	17	-1	7	63	-33	237	-197	71	-13	209
27	3	26	20	25	-20	0	30	-10	50	72	-14	209
28	2	3	25	-19	42	-1	31	-11	51	-367	425	209
29	1	-6	-11	46	22	-2	32	-12	52	73	-15	209
-151	135	93	-10	-11	-12	33	34	-13	53	74	-16	209
43	-74	-63	40	41	42	44	38	-14	54	75	-17	209
-2767	-2677	7659	-16	-17	-18	-19	-1985	20	-29	76	-18	209
2807	2717	-7619	56	57	58	59	2025	-29	20	77	-19	209
-7815	61	62	63	7589	64	65	66	67	68	29	-110	209
7873	-3	-4	-5	-7531	-6	-7	-8	-9	-10	-110	29	209
209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209

28	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										209
-86	128	25	26	27	28	-75	29	19	30	60	-2	209
37	38	-5	-6	-7	-8	95	-9	-15	31	61	-3	209
-110	130	28	57	-11	7	10	20	-19	39	62	-4	209
32	-12	16	20	25	20	33	-3	-20	40	63	-5	209
33	-13	13	25	11	32	9	21	165	-145	-286	344	209
34	-14	24	-21	56	22	8	22	-21	41	64	-6	209
35	-15	12	-48	85	11	15	36	-22	42	65	-7	209
36	-16	18	78	-55	19	36	15	-23	43	66	-8	209
89	-26	-26	200	-27	-28	-29	-30	43	-15	67	-9	209
51	-49	46	-180	47	48	49	50	44	45	68	-10	209
2965	2807	53	54	-7841	55	56	57	2025	59	29	-110	209
-2907	-2749	5	4	7899	3	2	1	-1967	-1	-110	29	209
209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209

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29	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										210	29	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										210
-30	62	-23	-24	-25	-26	302	-27	-28	-29	80	-22	210	29	35	-1	7	0	30	38	-18	-20	50	66	-6	210
61	60	53	54	55	56	-272	57	58	59	52	-83	210	26	20	25	-1	-1	31	39	-19	-21	51	67	-7	210
-33	63	29	30	-21	26	27	28	63	-32	45	-15	210	3	26	-1	42	63	-33	40	-20	-22	52	68	-8	210
-34	64	76	-22	51	4	3	2	-32	68	46	-16	210	12	-11	47	22	-2	32	-140	160	-23	53	69	-9	210
-35	65	3	27	29	65	-11	7	36	-6	47	-17	210	50	2	7	1	15	25	41	-21	281	-251	-330	390	210
-36	66	18	12	16	20	25	29	9	21	48	-18	210	-20	28	23	29	25	15	42	-22	-24	54	70	-10	210
372	-342	19	11	13	26	19	32	8	22	-216	246	210	34	124	35	-206	36	37	10	50	-25	55	71	-11	210
-37	67	20	10	32	-21	57	22	7	23	49	-19	210	-14	-104	-15	226	-16	-17	50	10	-26	56	72	-12	210
-38	68	-49	90	66	-1	-2	-3	24	25	50	-20	210	-436	-14	-15	-2877	-1995	5494	-18	-19	15	15	73	-13	210
-39	69	34	-8	-36	31	32	33	35	29	51	-21	210	466	44	45	2907	2025	-5464	48	49	15	15	74	-14	210
-67	-96	2907	38	39	40	-5012	41	42	2025	44	209	210	58	2908	59	60	-3100	61	62	63	64	65	30	-120	210
126	64	-2877	-8	-9	-10	5042	-11	-12	-1995	-86	-14	210	2	-2848	1	0	3160	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-120	30	210
210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210

29	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										210	29	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										210
38	39	-48	35	36	37	32	-59	-8	48	69	-9	210	-86	127	25	26	27	28	-75	29	19	30	60	0	210
121	-49	78	-5	-6	-7	-59	37	-9	49	70	-10	210	37	38	-5	-6	-7	-8	95	-9	-16	31	61	-1	210
-24	54	29	15	-1	7	63	-33	237	-197	71	-11	210	-110	130	29	55	-11	7	10	20	-19	39	62	-2	210
27	3	26	20	25	-21	0	30	-10	50	72	-12	210	32	-12	16	20	25	19	33	-3	-20	40	63	-3	210
28	2	3	26	-21	42	-1	31	-11	51	-357	417	210	33	-13	13	26	9	32	9	21	165	-145	-276	336	210
29	1	-8	-11	47	22	-2	32	-12	52	73	-13	210	34	-14	22	-21	57	22	8	22	-21	41	64	-4	210
-152	135	93	-10	-11	-12	33	34	-13	53	74	-14	210	35	-15	12	-50	87	11	15	35	-22	42	65	-5	210
43	-75	-63	40	41	42	44	38	-14	54	75	-15	210	36	-16	18	80	-57	19	35	15	-23	43	66	-6	210
-2867	-2779	7861	-16	-17	-18	-19	-1985	20	-30	76	-16	210	88	-25	-26	200	-27	-28	-29	-30	43	-16	67	-7	210
2907	2819	-7821	56	57	58	59	2025	-30	20	77	-17	210	51	-50	46	-180	47	48	49	50	44	45	68	-8	210
-8014	61	62	63	7798	64	65	66	67	68	30	-120	210	3066	2907	53	54	-8032	55	56	57	2025	59	30	-120	210
8074	-1	-2	-3	-7738	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-120	30	210	-3006	-2847	7	6	8092	5	4	3	-1965	1	-120	30	210
210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210

■ 211th Day of the Year - 30.07.2025

30	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											211
-30	62	-23	-24	-25	-26	302	-27	-28	-29	81	-22	211	211
61	60	53	54	55	56	-272	57	58	59	52	-82	211	211
-33	63	29	30	-21	26	27	28	64	-32	45	-15	211	211
-34	64	76	-22	51	4	3	2	-32	69	46	-16	211	211
-35	65	3	27	30	65	-11	7	36	-6	47	-17	211	211
-36	66	18	12	16	20	25	30	9	21	48	-18	211	211
372	-342	19	11	13	27	19	32	8	22	-216	246	211	211
-37	67	20	10	32	-21	58	22	7	23	49	-19	211	211
-38	68	-48	90	66	-1	-2	-3	24	25	50	-20	211	211
-39	69	34	-7	-36	31	32	33	35	29	51	-21	211	211
-66	-96	3007	38	39	40	-5112	41	42	2025	44	209	211	211
126	65	-2977	-8	-9	-10	5142	-11	-12	-1995	-86	-14	211	211
211	211	211	211	211	211	211	211	211	211	211	211	211	211

30	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											211
30	35	-1	7	0	30	38	-18	-20	50	66	-6	211	211
26	20	25	0	-1	31	39	-19	-21	51	67	-7	211	211
3	27	-1	42	63	-33	40	-20	-22	52	68	-8	211	211
12	-11	48	22	-2	32	-140	160	-23	53	69	-9	211	211
50	2	7	1	15	26	41	-21	281	-251	-330	390	211	211
-20	28	23	29	26	15	42	-22	-24	54	70	-10	211	211
34	125	35	-207	36	37	10	51	-25	55	71	-11	211	211
-14	-105	-15	227	-16	-17	51	10	-26	56	72	-12	211	211
-436	-14	-15	-2977	-1995	5594	-18	-19	15	16	73	-13	211	211
466	44	45	3007	2025	-5564	48	49	16	15	74	-14	211	211
58	3009	59	60	-3201	61	62	63	64	65	30	-119	211	211
2	-2949	1	0	3261	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-119	30	211	211
211	211	211	211	211	211	211	211	211	211	211	211	211	211

30	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											211
38	39	-48	35	36	37	33	-59	-8	48	69	-9	211	211
121	-49	78	-5	-6	-7	-59	38	-9	49	70	-10	211	211
-24	54	30	15	-1	7	63	-33	237	-197	71	-11	211	211
27	3	26	20	25	-20	0	30	-10	50	72	-12	211	211
28	2	3	27	-21	42	-1	31	-11	51	-357	417	211	211
29	1	-8	-11	48	22	-2	32	-12	52	73	-13	211	211
-151	135	93	-10	-11	-12	33	34	-13	53	74	-14	211	211
43	-74	-63	40	41	42	44	38	-14	54	75	-15	211	211
-2967	-2879	8061	-16	-17	-18	-19	-1985	20	-29	76	-16	211	211
3007	2919	-8021	56	57	58	59	2025	-29	20	77	-17	211	211
-8215	61	62	63	7999	64	65	66	67	68	30	-119	211	211
8275	-1	-2	-3	-7939	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-119	30	211	211
211	211	211	211	211	211	211	211	211	211	211	211	211	211

30	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											211
-86	128	25	26	27	28	-75	29	19	30	60	0	211	211
37	38	-5	-6	-7	-8	95	-9	-15	31	61	-1	211	211
-110	130	30	55	-11	7	10	20	-19	39	62	-2	211	211
32	-12	16	20	25	20	33	-3	-20	40	63	-3	211	211
33	-13	13	27	9	32	9	21	165	-145	-276	336	211	211
34	-14	22	-21	58	22	8	22	-21	41	64	-4	211	211
35	-15	12	-50	87	11	15	36	-22	42	65	-5	211	211
36	-16	18	80	-57	19	36	15	-23	43	66	-6	211	211
89	-26	-26	200	-27	-28	-29	-30	43	-15	67	-7	211	211
51	-49	46	-180	47	48	49	50	44	45	68	-8	211	211
3165	3007	53	54	-8231	55	56	57	2025	59	30	-119	211	211
-3105	-2947	7	6	8291	5	4	3	-1965	1	-119	30	211	211
211	211	211	211	211	211	211	211	211	211	211	211	211	211

■ 212th Day of the Year - 31.07.2025

31	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										212	31	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										212
-29	62	-22	-23	-24	-25	299	-26	-27	-28	76	-21	212	31	33	-1	7	0	30	38	-18	-20	50	66	-4	212
61	60	53	54	55	56	-268	57	58	59	52	-85	212	26	20	25	-1	-1	31	39	-19	-21	51	67	-5	212
-32	63	29	30	-21	26	27	28	63	-32	45	-14	212	3	28	-3	42	63	-33	40	-20	-22	52	68	-6	212
-33	64	76	-22	51	4	3	2	-32	68	46	-15	212	10	-11	49	22	-2	32	-140	160	-23	53	69	-7	212
-34	65	3	27	31	63	-11	7	36	-6	47	-16	212	52	2	5	1	15	25	41	-21	281	-251	-320	382	212
-35	66	18	12	16	20	25	29	9	21	48	-17	212	-22	28	25	29	25	15	42	-22	-24	54	70	-8	212
369	-338	19	11	13	28	17	32	8	22	-212	243	212	34	122	35	-204	36	37	10	50	-25	55	71	-9	212
-36	67	20	10	30	-21	59	22	7	23	49	-18	212	-14	-102	-15	224	-16	-17	50	10	-26	56	72	-10	212
-37	68	-49	90	66	-1	-2	-3	24	25	50	-19	212	-434	-14	-15	-3077	-1995	5692	-18	-19	15	15	73	-11	212
-38	69	34	-8	-36	31	32	33	35	29	51	-20	212	464	44	45	3107	2025	-5662	48	49	15	15	74	-12	212
-69	-94	3107	38	39	40	-5208	41	42	2025	44	207	212	58	3106	59	60	-3288	61	62	63	64	65	31	-129	212
125	60	-3076	-7	-8	-9	5239	-10	-11	-1994	-84	-13	212	4	-3044	3	2	3350	1	0	-1	-2	-3	-129	31	212
212	212	212	212	212	212	212	212	212	212	212	212	212	212	212	212	212	212	212	212	212	212	212	212	212	212

31	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										212	31	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										212
38	39	-48	35	36	37	32	-59	-8	48	69	-7	212	-86	127	25	26	27	28	-75	29	19	30	60	2	212
121	-49	78	-5	-6	-7	-59	37	-9	49	70	-8	212	37	38	-5	-6	-7	-8	95	-9	-16	31	61	1	212
-24	54	31	13	-1	7	63	-33	237	-197	71	-9	212	-110	130	31	53	-11	7	10	20	-19	39	62	0	212
27	3	26	20	25	-21	0	30	-10	50	72	-10	212	32	-12	16	20	25	19	33	-3	-20	40	63	-1	212
28	2	3	28	-23	42	-1	31	-11	51	-347	409	212	33	-13	13	28	7	32	9	21	165	-145	-266	328	212
29	1	-10	-11	49	22	-2	32	-12	52	73	-11	212	34	-14	20	-21	59	22	8	22	-21	41	64	-2	212
-152	135	93	-10	-11	-12	33	34	-13	53	74	-12	212	35	-15	12	-52	89	11	15	35	-22	42	65	-3	212
43	-75	-63	40	41	42	44	38	-14	54	75	-13	212	36	-16	18	82	-59	19	35	15	-23	43	66	-4	212
-3067	-2981	8263	-16	-17	-18	-19	-1985	20	-30	76	-14	212	88	-25	-26	200	-27	-28	-29	-30	43	-16	67	-5	212
3107	3021	-8223	56	57	58	59	2025	-30	20	77	-15	212	51	-50	46	-180	47	48	49	50	44	45	68	-6	212
-8414	61	62	63	8208	64	65	66	67	68	31	-129	212	3266	3107	53	54	-8422	55	56	57	2025	59	31	-129	212
8476	1	0	-1	-8146	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-129	31	212	-3204	-3045	9	8	8484	7	6	5	-1963	3	-129	31	212
212	212	212	212	212	212	212	212	212	212	212	212	212	212	212	212	212	212	212	212	212	212	212	212	212	212

5 Author's Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation Numbers

For author's contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation numbers** please see the links below:

- **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>
- **Inder J. Taneja**, Recreation of Numbers, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-recreation-of-numbers/>

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